

HyDelta 3

WP4b – Digitalization: decentralized hydrogen feed-in

D4b.1 – Controlling protocols and strategies for decentralized hydrogen feed-in

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Executive summary

In the HyDelta2 program several gaps in digitalization of the future (renewable) Distributed System Operator (DSO) gas grid were identified. One of them is that currently the DSOs do not have a uniform strategy to control the local feeder supplying to the grid in terms of gas quality, feed-in pressure and flow; in the frame of this work we focus on pressure and flow. Note that quality is covered in WP1 of the HyDelta3 program. In the future hydrogen grid, it is foreseen that there will be many distributed local hydrogen feeders in the partly new and partly existing gas distribution networks with a highly dynamic profile due to the wind and solar sources. Changing the pressure setting only in the beginning of the summer and winter will not be enough to sustain the security of supply, prioritization of feeders, and optimal feed-in of the local hydrogen suppliers.

Besides these technical challenges, from a legislative perspective there is still discussion/hesitation about the role of the DSOs in feeding-in gases in the distribution grid. From the perspective of the capacity of the grid. Different dynamic feed-in strategies have their pros and cons. These issues therefore need to be addressed.

For that reason, in the current HyDelta3 program the following research questions and activities have been defined on the topic of developing a controlling protocol for decentralized renewable gas feed-in for networks managed by the DSOs, with feeders and system requirements from both a legislative and technical point of view:

1. What is the role of DSOs and the procedure for controlling the gas quantities from feeders into their grid?
2. What is the standard procedure to guarantee security of supply of the gas feeder?
3. What is the equipment system needed to monitor and control the gas feeder?
4. How to dynamically control the pressure at the gas feeder to increase the feed-in flow limit and increase the uptime of the gas feeder?
5. What is the strategy to control (multiple) gas feeder prioritization for balancing the gas grid?
6. How will the control algorithm be affected when there is more flexibility in the system due to storage, flexible demand, and intermittent supply?

Two main activities were carried out to answer the above research questions.

The first activity answers research question 1, 2 and 3, aiming to provide the building blocks for a protocol for dynamic feed-in from a legislative point of view.

From a legislative perspective the role of the DSOs is still not fully defined in the current situation, and therefore it is not clear who is responsible for the future feed in of hydrogen in the distribution grid and balancing demand and supply. Almost all important matters that still need to be arranged have to do with the role and responsibilities of the DSOs. The main topics that should be arranged in a future protocol are:

- The roles and responsibilities of the DSOs in relation to third (private) parties, such as hydrogen producers.
- The responsibility for matching supply and demand and installing the appropriate hardware, such as buffers. Who decides on the criteria for e.g., pressure for switching off supply or demand?
- A prioritizing scheme for feed-in and/or switching off feeders and a clarity on who determines the optimal feed-in locations.

Additionally, there is also a need for a document that sets out the practical requirements concerning the feed-in; comparable to the Measuring and Control Protocol ('Beheersprotocol') as is used for biomethane. Main building blocks for this technical document are:

- Requirements of the physical connection to the gas grid
- Description of the measuring equipment and hardware in a 'gate keeper' for hydrogen feed-in.
- Requirements on data communication and data handling. Comparable with the current 'Meetvoorwaarden Gas Regionale Net Beheerders'. It is recommended to use the same demands for hydrogen as now are in use for biomethane.

The second activity is developing controlling strategies for a network with feed-in. This activity is related to research question 2, 4, 5 and 6.

This activity will focus on simulations and analysis about what is the control strategy to operate the grid for the gas feeder. Two use cases were investigated: one network for built environment covering multiple cities (Uden/Mill region) and one network for an industrial area in the port of Amsterdam.

The simulations were performed by the TNO tool AURORA, which is able to simulate flow, pressure and gas quality of complex gas grids for high pressure and low-pressure networks. Both the static and dynamic solver can be used.

In total two use cases were performed with the following grids: Enexis (Uden/Mill) and Alliander (H2avennet). Uden/Mill is a domestic area with five GOS's and three planned green gas feeders. For the investigation in the frame of this study the green gas feeders are replaced by hydrogen feeders, where we assume a three times higher flow because of the energy ratio between hydrogen and natural gas. The 8-bar grid in the area has been investigated, with the currently available setpoints for pressure and feed-in flow. The demands take place on district station level, where the same flow dynamics are assumed as in the GOS. GOS flow measurement data is available.

The H2avennet use case is a planned hydrogen grid in the port of Amsterdam with three import stations, a biomass gasification feeder and an electrolyser. On the demand side there are three feedstock and six heat consumers foreseen. The pressure of the grid will be maximum 16 bar. The foreseen profiles for all supply and demand are given by Alliander for the scope of this study.

Together with the DSOs involved in this work package several scenarios were defined for the two use cases. For Uden-Mill three cases are investigated:

- A) Impact of outages. Three days in the winter season, where subsequently three, two and one feeder shut down. Using both static and dynamic analysis.
- B) Priority of feeders. Three days in the summer, where the hydrogen feeders flowrate will be adjusted when the pressure is higher than setpoint pressure. The three feeders got an (artificially determined) priority.
- C) Possible location for a booster. In the summer season, three days where the total demand is lower than the total feed-in (according to contract). Only one booster can be deployed in the network, next to a WOS.

For H2avennet the following cases have been studied:

- A) Impact of availability of renewable sources like wind. A period of one week simulation, where the electrolyzer follows the wind speed profile. The biomass gasification feeder has a fixed

production profile and two hydrogen imports have a fixed pressure setpoint. There is no connection to the TSO network.

- B) Impact of placement of an additional hydrogen feeder. The same scenario as above, but with an extra feeder where the optimal location is investigated.

Several observations and conclusions can be derived from the studied scenarios regarding main lessons learned and guidelines for asset management with multiple local feed-in and dynamic supply and demand.

A transient analysis tool is needed to understand the system dynamics.

Both case studies show that the linepack capacity of the network is too small compared to the feeder flow variations. Thus, there is a fast reaction time (within minutes) needed in order to maintain the pressure in operating conditions. A transient solver can help DSOs to design the control strategy of their grid management (flow balancing, pressure dynamics, etc.). Especially in the case of emergency or a sudden failure. Next to the safety components already available in the grid to prevent damage to the grid and the customers.

Static pressure management for prioritization is not straightforward when there are many local feeders, but it can be done.

When the network is only having one or two local feeders, static pressure management (two setpoints per year) is sufficient for managing the grid. However, it is complicated to control the correct order in which feeders are shut down in case of oversupply with multiple local feeders. Since the demand and supply has high uncertainties (weather dependent), it is unclear when one should change the setpoint pressure and how many times in a year due to big difference in minimum flow and maximum flow demand in a year.

Dynamic pressure management is a more robust solution (from capacity perspective) but requires more technologies

Since there is a lot of dynamics in production and demand, utilizing dynamic pressure management can be a robust solution because the grid is dynamically controlled to react in the current situation. This method requires more real-time flow and pressure data, real-time algorithms to determine the flow and pressure setpoint at regulators and remote actuators for controlling valve.

Setpoint pressure of the WOS can be utilized to increase capacity and uptime of the hydrogen feeder

To increase the capacity and uptime of the hydrogen feeder during the low demand season, one can set the setpoint pressure of the WOS close to minimum pipeline pressure compared to the setting during high demand season where the setpoint pressure is close to maximum pipeline pressure. Thus, there is not enough room for hydrogen feeder's delta pressure. The higher delta pressure, the more capacity can be facilitated.

Setpoint pressure control can be deployed for feeder prioritization

In the studied cases, the priority of the WOS and feeder can be set by putting the correct setpoint pressure for their pressure regulator. With help of a simulation tool, one can estimate what is the required pressure to guaranty a certain flow. One can prioritize by giving the lowest setpoint pressure to the lowest priority feeder and the highest setpoint pressure to the highest priority feeder. In the current regulation, first come first served basis is used to determine the priority of the feeder.

A booster can be used to increase local feeder uptime, but not in every location

Booster implementation can increase the uptime of the local. It is recommended to implement a booster near to the local feeder to avoid a high pressure drop due to distance. In practice it should be also near a RTL pipeline and a GOS.

Surface storage is not a practical solution due to seasonal imbalance

In general the imbalance in the low demand period, which is several months, is too high to store the surplus of hydrogen in practical available storage tanks. In case of daily to weekly storage more practical solutions will be available.

General conclusion

The research activities done in this HyDelta3 work package and a case study in two different networks give several insights in how to control the future hydrogen grid in case there will be more distributed local hydrogen feeders. Digitalization can help to design a more robust grid or improve operational excellence. A profile-based simulation tool can help the grid operator to make decisions about which solution should be implemented to increase the capacity and controlling the feeders. Based on measurement data from past years and weather profiles, we can predict the consumption profiles. Then one can determine the period and with capacity in a year, where the feeder supply is higher than the total demand. Thus, DSOs can determine which solution should be implemented: e.g. a booster station, curtailment of the feeder, pressure management or surface/sub-surface storage.

Samenvatting

In het HyDelta2-programma zijn verschillende hiaten in de digitalisering van het toekomstige (hernieuwbare) gas netwerk van de Distributie Systeembeheerder (DSO) geïdentificeerd. Een van deze hiaten is dat de huidige DSO's geen uniforme strategie hebben om de lokale toevoer naar het netwerk te controleren op het gebied van gaskwaliteit, invoerdruk en -flow. Binnen dit werk richten we ons op druk en flow. Gaskwaliteit wordt behandeld in WP1 van het HyDelta3-programma. In het toekomstige waterstofnet wordt voorzien dat er veel gedistribueerde lokale waterstofproducenten zullen zijn in de deels nieuwe en deels bestaande gasdistributienetwerken, met een zeer dynamisch profiel door de wind- en zonnebronnen. Alleen de drukinstelling aan het begin van de zomer en winter aanpassen zal niet voldoende zijn om de leveringszekerheid, prioritering van producenten en optimale invoer van lokale waterstofleveranciers te waarborgen.

Naast deze technische uitdagingen is er vanuit wetgevend perspectief nog steeds discussie/twijfel over de rol van de DSO's bij het invoeren van gassen in het distributienetwerk. Vanuit het perspectief van de capaciteit van het netwerk. Verschillende dynamische invoerstrategieën hebben hun voor- en nadelen. Deze kwesties moeten daarom worden geadresseerd.

Om die reden zijn in het huidige HyDelta3-programma de volgende onderzoeksvragen en activiteiten gedefinieerd met betrekking tot het ontwikkelen van een controleprotocol voor gedecentraliseerde invoer van hernieuwbaar gas voor netwerken beheerd door de DSO's, met toevoerbronnen en systeemvereisten, vanuit zowel wetgevend als technisch oogpunt:

1. Wat is de rol van DSO's en de procedure voor het controleren van de gashoeveelheden van producenten naar hun netwerk?
2. Wat is de standaardprocedure om de leveringszekerheid van de gastoevoer te garanderen?
3. Wat is het benodigde apparaat en systeem om de gastoevoer te monitoren en te controleren?
4. Hoe kan de druk bij de gastoevoer dynamisch worden geregeld om de invoerstroombreedte te verhogen en de uptime van de gastoevoer te vergroten?
5. Wat is de strategie en prioritering om te sturen op (meerdere) gastoevoer, voor het balanceren van het gasnet?
6. Hoe wordt het controlealgoritme beïnvloed wanneer er meer flexibiliteit in het systeem is door opslag, flexibele vraag en intermitterende levering?

Er zijn twee activiteiten gedaan in dit werkpakket, om de bovenstaande onderzoeksvragen te beantwoorden.

De eerste activiteit beantwoordt onderzoeksvragen 1, 2 en 3 en biedt de bouwstenen voor een protocol voor dynamische invoer vanuit wetgevend perspectief.

Vanuit wetgevend oogpunt is de rol van de DSO's in de huidige situatie nog niet volledig gedefinieerd, en daarom is het niet duidelijk wie verantwoordelijk is voor de toekomstige invoer van waterstof in het distributienetwerk en het balanceren van vraag en aanbod. Bijna alle belangrijke zaken die nog moeten worden geregeld, hebben te maken met de rol en verantwoordelijkheden van de DSO's. De belangrijkste onderwerpen die in een toekomstig protocol moeten worden geregeld zijn:

- De rollen en verantwoordelijkheden van de DSO's in relatie tot derde (particuliere) partijen zoals waterstofproducenten.
- De verantwoordelijkheid voor het afstemmen van vraag en aanbod en het installeren van de juiste hardware zoals buffers. En, wie beslist over de criteria voor bijvoorbeeld de druk voor het uitschakelen van aanvoer of vraag?

- Er is een prioriteitschema nodig voor invoer en/of uitschakeling van invoeders en het moet duidelijk zijn wie de optimale invoerlocaties bepaalt.

Daarnaast is er ook behoefte aan een document dat de praktische vereisten voor de invoer uiteenzet; vergelijkbaar met het Meet- en Regelprotocol ('Beheersprotocol') zoals dat wordt gebruikt voor groen gas. De belangrijkste bouwstenen voor dit technische document zijn:

- Vereisten voor de fysieke aansluiting op het gasnet.
- Beschrijving van de meetapparatuur en hardware in een 'poortwachter' voor waterstofinvoer.
- Vereisten voor datacommunicatie en data-afhandeling. Vergelijkbaar met de huidige 'Meetvoorwaarden Gas Regionale Netbeheerders'. Het wordt aanbevolen om dezelfde eisen voor waterstof te gebruiken als die nu gelden voor groen gas.

De tweede activiteit is het ontwikkelen van regelstrategieën voor een netwerk met invoer. Deze activiteit heeft betrekking op onderzoeksvraag 2, 4, 5 en 6.

Deze activiteit zal zich richten op simulaties en analyses over wat de control strategie is om het netwerk te beheren voor de gastoevoer. Er worden twee 'use cases' onderzocht: één netwerk voor de bebouwde omgeving die meerdere steden omvat (regio Uden/Mill) en één netwerk voor een industriegebied in de haven van Amsterdam.

De simulaties werden uitgevoerd met de TNO-tool AURORA, die in staat is om flow, druk en gaskwaliteit van complexe gasnetwerken voor hoge- en lagedruk te simuleren. Zowel de statische als de dynamische rekenkern kan worden gebruikt.

In totaal werden twee use cases uitgevoerd, voor een Enexis (Uden/Mill) en Alliander (H2avennet) netwerk. Uden/Mill is een woongebied met vijf GOS's en drie geplande groengas-toevoeren. Voor het onderzoek in het kader van deze studie worden de groengas-toevoeren vervangen door waterstoftoevoeren, waarbij we een drie keer hogere flow aannemen vanwege de energieratio tussen waterstof en aardgas. Het 8-bar netwerk in het gebied is onderzocht, met de momenteel beschikbare setpoints voor druk en flow. De vraag vindt plaats op het niveau van de wijkstations, waarbij dezelfde flow dynamiek wordt aangenomen als in de GOS. GOS-flowmeetgegevens zijn beschikbaar.

De H2avennet 'use case' is een gepland waterstofnetwerk in de haven van Amsterdam met drie invoerstations, een biomassa-vergassingsinstallatie en een elektrolyser. Aan de vraagzijde worden drie grondstoffen- en zes warmteverbruikers voorzien. De druk van het netwerk zal maximaal 16 bar zijn. De voorziene profielen voor alle aanvoer en vraag worden door Alliander verstrekt voor de scope van deze studie.

Samen met de DSO's die betrokken zijn bij dit werkpakket, zijn verschillende scenario's gedefinieerd voor de twee use cases. Voor Uden-Mill worden drie gevallen onderzocht:

A) Impact van uitval. Drie dagen in het winterseizoen, waarbij achtereenvolgens drie, twee en één feeder uitvallen. Gebruikmakend van zowel statische als dynamische analyse.

B) Prioriteit van feeders. Drie dagen in de zomer, waarbij de flow van de waterstoftoevoeren wordt aangepast wanneer de druk hoger is dan de setpointdruk. De drie feeders kregen een (kunstmatig bepaalde) prioriteit.

C) Mogelijke locatie voor een booster. In het zomerseizoen, drie dagen waarbij de totale vraag lager is dan de totale invoer (volgens contract). Slechts één booster kan in het netwerk worden geplaatst, naast een WOS.

Voor H2avennet zijn de volgende gevallen bestudeerd:

A) Impact van beschikbaarheid van hernieuwbare bronnen zoals wind. Een simulatieperiode van één week, waarbij de elektrolyser het windsnelheidsprofiel volgt. De biomassa-vergassingsinstallatie heeft een vast productieprofiel en twee waterstofimporten hebben een vaste druksetpoint. Er is geen verbinding met het TSO-netwerk.

B) Impact van plaatsing van een extra waterstoftoevoer. Hetzelfde scenario als hierboven, maar met een extra toevoer waarbij de optimale locatie wordt onderzocht.

Uit de bestudeerde scenario's kunnen verschillende observaties en conclusies worden getrokken met betrekking tot de belangrijkste geleerde lessen en richtlijnen voor asset management met meerdere lokale invoerpunten en dynamische vraag en aanbod.

Een tijdsafhankelijk analysesysteem is nodig om de systeemdynamiek te begrijpen.

Beide casestudies laten zien dat de linepack-capaciteit van het netwerk te klein is in vergelijking met de variaties in de toevoer van de feeder. Daarom is een snelle reactietijd (binnen enkele minuten) nodig om de druk in bedrijfsomstandigheden te handhaven. Een tijdsafhankelijke tool kan DSO's helpen bij het ontwerpen van de controlestrategie voor hun netbeheer (flow balancering, drukdynamiek, enz.). Vooral in geval van nood of een plotselinge storing. Dit alles naast de veiligheidscomponenten die nu al geïnstalleerd zijn in het grid om schade aan het netwerk en eindgebruikers te voorkomen.

Statisch drukbeheer voor prioritering is niet eenvoudig wanneer er veel lokale producenten zijn, maar het is mogelijk.

Wanneer het netwerk slechts één of twee lokale producenten heeft, is statisch drukbeheer (twee setpoints per jaar) voldoende voor het beheer van het netwerk. Het is echter ingewikkeld om de juiste volgorde te beheersen waarin de producenten worden afgesloten in geval van overaanbod met meerdere lokale toevoerleidingen. Aangezien de vraag en het aanbod grote onzekerheden kennen (weerafhankelijk), is het onduidelijk wanneer men de druk moet wijzigen en hoe vaak in een jaar, vanwege het grote verschil in minimum- en maximumdebietvraag in een jaar.

Een dynamische drukbeheersing is een robuustere oplossing (vanuit capaciteitsoogpunt), maar vereist meer technologieën.

Aangezien er veel dynamiek is in productie en vraag, kan het gebruik van dynamische drukbeheersing een robuuste oplossing zijn omdat het net dynamisch wordt gecontroleerd om te reageren op de huidige situatie. Deze methode vereist meer realtime flow- en drukgegevens, realtime algoritmen om de flow- en druksetpoint te bepalen bij regelaars en externe actuatoren voor het regelen van de klep.

De insteldruk van de WOS kan worden gebruikt om de capaciteit en beschikbaarheid van de waterstofinvoer te verhogen.

Om de capaciteit en beschikbaarheid van de waterstofinvoer tijdens het laagseizoen te verhogen, kan men de insteldruk van de WOS dicht bij de minimale pijpleidingdruk instellen vergeleken met de instelling tijdens het hoogseizoen waar de insteldruk dicht bij de maximale pijpleidingdruk ligt. Hierdoor is er niet genoeg ruimte voor de drukverandering van de waterstofinvoer. Hoe hoger de drukverandering, hoe meer capaciteit kan worden gefaciliteerd.

Druksturing kan worden ingezet voor prioritering van de toevoer.

In de bestudeerde gevallen kan de prioriteit van de WOS en de feeder worden ingesteld door de juiste druk in te stellen voor hun drukregelaar. Met behulp van een simulatietool kan men schatten wat de vereiste druk is om een bepaalde flow te garanderen. Men kan prioriteit geven door de laagste druk te geven aan de minst belangrijke feeder en de hoogste druk aan de belangrijkste feeder. In de huidige regelgeving wordt 'wie eerst komt, eerst maalt' gebruikt om de prioriteit van de feeder te bepalen.

Een booster kan worden gebruikt om de beschikbaarheid van de lokale feeder te verhogen, maar niet op elke locatie.

De implementatie van een booster kan de beschikbaarheid van de lokale feeder verhogen. Het wordt aanbevolen om een booster nabij de lokale feeder te implementeren om een hoge drukval door afstand te vermijden. In de praktijk moet het ook dicht bij een RTL-pijpleiding en een GOS zijn.

Bovengrondse opslag is geen praktische oplossing vanwege seizoensgebonden onbalans.

Over het algemeen is de onbalans in de periode van lage vraag, die enkele maanden duurt, te groot om het overschot aan waterstof op te slaan in praktisch beschikbare opslagtanks. In geval van dagelijkse tot wekelijkse opslag zullen meer praktische oplossingen beschikbaar zijn.

Algemene conclusie

De onderzoeksactiviteiten in dit HyDelta3-werkpakket en een casestudy in twee verschillende netwerken geven verschillende inzichten in hoe het toekomstige waterstofnetwerk kan worden geregeld in geval van meer gedistribueerde lokale waterstofinvoeren. Digitalisering kan helpen bij het ontwerpen van een robuuster netwerk of het verbeteren van operationele uitvoerbaarheid. Een op profielen gebaseerde simulatietool kan de netbeheerder helpen bij het nemen van beslissingen over welke oplossing moet worden geïmplementeerd om de capaciteit te verhogen en de invoer te regelen. Op basis van meetgegevens van voorgaande jaren en weersprofielen kunnen we de consumptieprofielen voorspellen. Vervolgens kan men de periode en de capaciteit in een jaar bepalen, waarbij de invoer van de feeder hoger is dan de totale vraag. Dus, DSO's kunnen bepalen welke oplossing moet worden geïmplementeerd: bijvoorbeeld een boosterstation, reductie van de feeder capaciteit, drukbeheer of boven-/ondergrondse opslag.

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Abbreviation List

Abbreviation	Description
ATEX	Atmosphères Explosibles. The minimum safety requirements for workplaces and equipment used in explosive atmospheres.
ATO	Aansluit- en Transportovereenkomst/Connection and Transport Agreement
DSO	Distribution System Operator (e.g. Stedin, Alliander, Enexis, Coteq) or
ESD	Emergency Shut Down System. An automatic protection system which will act to shut down the valve
EVHI	Elektronische Volume Herleiding Instrument/Electronic Volume Corrector Instrument
GOS	Gas Ontvangst Station/Gas Receiving Station. A city gate station of natural gas from high pressure network to low pressure network
KNMI	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut/Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute
TSO	Transmission System Operator (e.g. Gasunie)
WOS	Waterstof Ontvangst Station/Hydrogen Receiving Station. A city gate station of hydrogen from high pressure network to low pressure network ¹
NG	Natural gas
H2	Hydrogen
HTL	Main transmission network
RTL	Regional transmission network
RNB	Regionale netbeheerders
OS	Overslagstations
DS	District Station

¹ Hynetwork Services uses the term Hydrogen Delivery Station (HDS)

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The state of the art of digitalization of the existing gas network infrastructure in the Netherlands has been discussed in the previous HyDelta 2.0 program [1]. Several gaps in digitalization of the future (renewable) Distributed System Operator (DSO) grid were identified. One of the topics is that currently the DSOs do not have a uniform strategy to control the local feeder (in this case green gas feeder) supplying to the grid in terms of gas quality², feed-in pressure and flow. Each operator has their own strategy to control the local feeder, from a passive control by monitoring the gas quality of the feeder and demand the feeder to close when there is a need, to an active control where they install additional valves downstream of the feeder (gate keeper) to protect their grid.

In the future hydrogen grid, the gas network infrastructure will be similar. The current green gas feeder is equivalent to the future hydrogen feeder to the grid in terms of as a local feeder. It is projected there will be many distributed local hydrogen feeders in the distribution network using a power-to-H₂ conversion technology, which in most cases will be an electrolyser. However green gas feeder and hydrogen feeder will have different characteristic of flow. The green gas feeder usually has a constant flowrate while the hydrogen produced from an electrolyzer depends of the electrical power that may be coming from renewable energy sources (e.g., wind turbine or solar panel) that has an intermittency. With respect to the green gas feeder the bottleneck normally occurs during summer time when there is low gas demand. So, by reducing the pressure setting of the grid one time in the beginning of summer and increasing it in the beginning of winter, this can reduce the green gas pressure control problem in most cases. However, with respect to the hydrogen feeder, the production is not constant due to the intermittency and variability of renewable electricity sources and the congestion in the electricity grid. Also, there is no clear pattern from wind between summer and winter. Thus, controlling the pressure of the feeder is not simple and straightforward.

Besides these technical challenges, from a legislative perspective there is still discussion about the responsibilities of the DSOs in feeding-in gases in the distribution grid from a technical capability perspective. All the different dynamic feed-in strategies have their pros and cons. These issues therefore need to be addressed. With dynamic feed-in we define the active control of the feed-in flow by adjusting the setpoint of the feeders and WOS, pressure or flow, at every time step for a given goal (e.g. to maximize the feed-in flow of the feeders).

² Gas quality is part of WP1 of the HyDelta 3 project and therefore not further discussed in this report

Figure 1 Concept of future hydrogen grid where there are more assets and devices in the system (e.g. storage, booster, local feeder, sensor and remote valve)

1.2 Research objectives and questions

Based on the problem statement in the previous section, the research objective of this study is “How to develop a controlling protocol for decentralized renewable gas feed-in for networks managed by the DSOs, including an ATO (*Aansluit- en Transport-Overeenkomst (NL)*: Connection and Transport Agreement (EN)) with feeders and system requirements.”

The research questions that will be investigated in the frame of this study, as formulated in the HyDelta3 proposal, are given below:

1. What is the role of DSOs and the procedure for controlling the gas quantities from feeders into their grid?
2. What is the standard procedure to guarantee security of supply of the gas feeder?
3. What is the equipment system needed to monitor and control the gas feeder’s flow limit and production capacity?
4. How to dynamically control the pressure at the gas feeder to increase the feed-in flow limit and increase the uptime of the gas feeder?
5. What is the strategy to control (multiple) gas feeder prioritization for balancing the gas grid?
6. How will the control algorithm be affected when there is more flexibility in the system due to storage, flexible demand, and intermittent supply?

1.3 Research activities

To answer the research questions two research activities have been defined:

1. Providing the building blocks for a protocol for dynamic feed-in from a legislative point of view

This activity is related to research question 1, 2 and 3.

In this activity, a gap analysis will be performed and recommendations will be made on the basis of that analysis on roles and responsibilities of the different actors involved. This analysis is focusing

on dynamic pressure and flow control and taking into account the possible differences between green gas feeder parameters/variables and hydrogen feeder parameters; see chapter 2.

2. Develop controlling strategies for a network with feed-in

This activity is related to research question 2, 4, 5 and 6.

This activity will focus on simulation and analysis about what is the control strategy to operate the grid in case of several gas feeders. There are two use cases investigated: one network for built environment covering multiple cities and one network for an industrial area in the harbour. The focus of the study will be on controlling the gas network to guarantee security of supply of the gas feeder, taking into account the boundaries of the given gas network. A dynamic pressure algorithm will be deployed to allow balancing supply and demand in the grid. See chapter 3.

2. Building blocks for a protocol for dynamic feed-in

This chapter describes the investigation of building blocks for a protocol for dynamic feed-in, based on actual supply and demand of hydrogen. The aimed future protocol has to deal with the regulatory aspects of feeding in of hydrogen.

The responsibilities regarding supply, storage, transport, distribution and end use for natural gas are laid down in the Dutch Gas Act (Gaswet [2]), Codes [3] and Ministerial Regulations [4] . This has not yet been arranged for hydrogen. It is expected that hydrogen will be aligned as much as possible with the current legislation for natural gas. However, there are a number of significant differences between the two gases, which need to be settled prior a wider use of hydrogen.

One of the deliverables within Work Package 4b of HyDelta3 is providing a list of topics that are not (fully) provided for in the current legislation and that must be resolved through adjustments in the regulatory domain.

2.1 Roles and responsibilities

Almost all important matters that still need to be arranged have to do with responsibilities. In particular, the role and responsibilities of the regional grid operators (DSO) are still unclear. The most important questions that need to be answered are listed below:

- Will the (regional) grid operator be obliged to take in hydrogen?
- Who will be responsible for facilitating the transport and distribution of hydrogen (eq. grid operators or also private parties)?
- How should be dealt with fluctuating patterns?
 - Who will be responsible for matching supply and demand and may install buffers, compressors, etc.?
- What are the criteria for switching off supply and/or demand (eq. maximum pressure)?
- What is the procedure when more than one feed-in points are connected to the same grid?
 - What prioritizing scheme should be used for feed-in and/or switching off feeders (eq. first-come-first-serve, based on capacities)?
- Who will be responsible for solving the congestion in the electricity network by producing hydrogen?
- What is the best technical and economical solution for operating a hydrogen network, based on the lowest social costs and technical & safety aspects?
 - Who determines the optimal point for feed-in?

A supposed table of contents for a document where the above questions are answered is given in Table 1. It is suspected that the mentioned items will be further elaborated by the Regulatory Workgroup of Netbeheer Nederland and their discussion with the Ministry of Economic Affairs will be coordinated by this Workgroup.

Table 1 – Regulatory aspects hydrogen: proposed table of contents

1.	Introduction
	Short explanation and objective
2.	Laws, Codes
	Overview of the documents that must be complied with: Eg. (municipal) permits and zoning plans, environmental permits, etc.

	<p>Questions to be answered:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Will the grid operator be obliged to take in hydrogen? • Who will be responsible for facilitating the hydrogen? • Who will be responsible for matching supply and demand (eq. buffering, compression, etc.)? • Reducing future Electricity grid-congestion by making hydrogen: Who? • Decision tree. What is the best technical and economical regulatory system (balance between lowest social costs and technical aspects)
3.	Feed-in
3.1.	Registration procedure (producer)
	<p>Where to register Expected maximal capacity and production capacity Expected start date Commodity supplier (transport)</p>
3.2.	Gas network management (grid operator)
	<p>Determination of the most optimal place for feed-in Providing a time lime: when is the grid operational for hydrogen distribution? Gas network management: dynamic or static (maximum) pressure? How to handle supply > demand? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Switching off supply? • Buffer (where? How to decide) • Booster (where? How to decide) How to deal with strongly fluctuating pattern? Calamity procedure (switching off)</p>
3.3.	Prioritizing – How to handle more than one feed-in points (who is responsible?)
	<p>Who decides? Based on which criteria: Capacity? First-come-first-serve? Pressure settings? Circumstances for switching off (based on safety aspects: max. pressure?)</p>

2.2 Technical requirements

In addition to the regulatory aspects that need to be arranged, there is also a need for a document that sets out the practical requirements concerning the feed-in. The document is comparable to the Measuring and Control Protocol (Beheersprotocol [5]) as is used for biomethane. The gas quality is subject to Work Package 1a of the HyDelta3 project and therefore not further discussed in this report.

A suggested table of contents for such a document is given in Table 2. The technical part can be divided into a number of subjects:

1. Requirements of the physical connection to the gas grid. In order to be able to shut off the feed-in and to control the pressure of the upstream gas grid, the grid operator needs to place a feed-in station. The station will at least consist of a manual valve and, depending on the requirements of the grid operator, a pressure reducer can also be installed to protect the upstream network. The physical location of the station should be determined by the grid operator, taking into account the accessibility and the safety measures to be taken (eq. ATEX and risk contours).
2. At the end of the installation, the supplier must install a so-called gatekeeper. This gatekeeper contains the necessary measuring equipment in order to demonstrate that the hydrogen meets the quality and complies to the physical properties as is prescribed in the Codes and/or

Ministerial Regulation, similar to the present situation for biomethane feed-in. Furthermore the necessary equipment for custody transfer should be installed. For each parameter, the minimal accuracy, calibration and maintenance frequency should be prescribed. The gatekeeper should contain at least one mechanical pressure regulator, which is adjusted to a pressure as is agreed with the grid operator.

3. All measured values should be logged in a Programmable Logic Computer (PLC). For each parameter the upper and lower warning (resp. H and L) and alarm values (HH and LL), should be programmed. When a value exceeds one of the alarm values the feed-in should be stopped automatically by closing an emergency shutdown (ESD) valve. In the event of emergencies or in situations where off-spec gas is not switched off, the grid operator must be able to operate the ESD remotely.
4. As now also is described in the document ‘Meetvoorwaarden Gas’ [6], all data should be stored and saved in a non-volatile database for a period of time. Furthermore, it must be recorded who may have access to the data and which disclaimers must be observed, for example in the case of misinterpretation. It is recommended to use the same demands for hydrogen as now are in use for biomethane.

Table 2 – Proposed table of contents for a Measuring and Control Protocol for hydrogen feed-in

1.	Introduction
	Short explanation and objective
2.	Norms, Codes of Practice, Technical Standards
	Overview of the documents that must be complied with
3.	Technical Requirements Hardware (physical place for feed-in)
3.1.	Requirements gas grid connection
	Minimal requirements for feed-in station (‘druk bewakingstation’): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hand valve? • Pressure protection? • Minimal distance to the gas grid (e.g. based on risk contours/ ATEX zone) • Accessibility: above ground level or well? • Protection against weather influences
3.2.	Requirements gate keeper
	Gas quality: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hydrogen purity (accuracy) • Trace components: which ones. Ranges. Accuracy per component • Per component: requirements for calibration, maintenance/service interval Physical parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pressure: Range and accuracy • Temperature: Range and accuracy • Flow: Range and accuracy (Elektronische Volume Herleiding Instrument, EVHI)? • Water dewpoint: Range and accuracy • Per parameter: requirements for calibration, maintenance/service interval Odorization: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which odorant. Range and accuracy Alarms: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Per component or parameter: Warning and alarm levels (HH, H, L, LL) • What to do when the communication with a sensor is lost?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determination of maximal lost sensors <p>Safety and protection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emergency shut down valve (ESD) • Mechanical pressure control • Protection against weather influences: minimal IP rating, grounding, lightning strike • ATEX zone
3.3.	Communication box
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability data: hard wired, cloud? • Cyber security • Resolution: number of measurements per hour • Communication protocol (See Aansluitvoorwaarden Gas [7]) • Version control • Applicability: it should be possible to run old data sets with newer software versions • How and where: non-volatile database? • Minimal term of storage: 5 years? • Uninterruptible Power Supply, UPS?
3.4.	Data handling
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scope: description of where the information may be used for • Who may use this information? Grid operators, hydrogen producers, etc. • Incorrect interpretation and/or use of the information • What to do in case of conflicts? • Disclaimer and/or liability: • Public accessibility

3. Controlling strategies for a network with feed-in

In the previous chapter, building blocks for a protocol for dynamic feed-in of hydrogen has been discussed. In this chapter, we will focus on testing several control strategies for hydrogen feed-in from technical perspectives. Starting from designing feeder's pressure setting for adhering the maximum and minimum pipeline pressure. Furthermore, investigating the dynamic behaviour of the network when there is imbalance of supply and demand, evaluating the reaction time for the control system when there is sudden failure, designing workflow for prioritizing the feeders when there is over supply, and evaluating the location of booster station or storage sizing needed. Not all questions in chapter 1 regarding technical requirements are addressed in this chapter.

3.1 Methodology

3.1.1 Gas Network Simulation Tool

In order to run the analysis for this report, we use an in-house TNO gas network simulation tool called Aurora (Figure 2). This simulation tool consists of two different algorithms: quasi-steady state solver and transient solver. This tool can be used both for high pressure transmission networks and low pressure distribution networks.

In principle the transient flow in a network element such as a pipe can be described by the following (coupled) dynamic (differential) equations:

- Mass conservation equation (equation of continuity).
- Newton's second law of motion (conservation of momentum).
- Energy equation (thermodynamic first law)
- Equation describing gas properties as function of pressure and temperature (equation of state)

With simplification of 'isothermal' and 'one-dimensional' one ends up with a practical number of solvable equations.

Figure 2 Aurora: an in-house TNO gas simulator tool. It is a web-based tool that can simulate the pressure, flow, gas composition of the gas network. The results can be presented as snapshot/animation in geographic information systems (GIS) based and visualized as a time series plot.

3.1.2 Hydrogen Feeder control

In the future of hydrogen network, it is expected to have more distributed hydrogen production via electrolyzers (power to hydrogen) or biomass gasification. The electrolyzers can help to balance the electricity grid congestion by producing hydrogen. In the future, the use of gas for residential heating will decline and fluctuate with the introduction of conventional or hybrid heat pumps. As a result, the imbalance of the gas grid is expected on some occasions. Thus, gas balancing of the grid and prioritization of the feeder will become more a challenge. DSOs have already experienced this question in introducing green gas feeder in the current grid. Gasunie, the TSO owner and operator in The Netherlands, presented the intentions for increasing drastically the feed-in of green gas in the existing gas grid in their presentation “Presentatie t.b.v. groen gas marktplan” [8]. In the same presentation, it is explained that the green gas feeders will require some network adjustments to ensure a balanced grid. Below, with figure the infrastructure adjustments are illustrated.

Figure 3 Presentation by Gasunie [8] about the adjustments to the gas transmission and distribution infrastructure. 1 is connecting producer to a higher network level, 2 is buffering or storage at the producer, 3 is storage or pressure management by DSO or Regionale netbeheerders (RNB), 4 is combine with constant-demand customers (industry), 5 is grid connections between DSOs and 6 is gas boosters.

There are several methods to increase the capacity of the injection or balancing the grid, e.g., using the line-pack capacity of the pipe, using storage facility (surface or sub surface), managing pressure of the pipeline (static or dynamic), adding a booster station or curtailment of the feeder. In this report we will only investigate two methods: (static) pressure management and adding a booster station.

A. Linepack capacity or storage

Linepack describes the total of volume of gas contained within the pipe. Gas is a compressible fluid, thus it will change volume under varying pressure. When there is imbalance of supply and demand in the grid, it will result in pressure fluctuations in the grid. When the gas volume in the pipe is increasing, then the pressure is increasing and vice versa. The network operator need to maintain the pipeline pressure within a certain operational pressure boundaries. Next to linepack volume for balancing the grid, the surface tank storage or sub-surface (underground storage), can be utilized also to balance between supply and demand to maintain the grid pressure. Thus, it can create more capacity for the feeder.

B. Pressure Management

A DSO operator has an agreement about the setpoint pressure of the GOS connection stations and the green gas feeding points. Current practice is that they change the pressure of the GOS two times a year: during winter and summer to create more capacity in the grid and allow the green gas feeder to inject during the low-demand season. This process is called 'static' due to it has to be changed manually by sending engineers to the field. It is not yet an automated process (which is called dynamic pressure management) where the setpoint pressure can be changed automatically with a more frequent

interval based on pressure and flow sensors in the grid, while maintaining minimum and maximum pressure of the grid.

Figure 4 Illustration of dynamic pressure management using sensor telemetry and remote control

C. Booster Station

A booster station is one of the solutions for balancing the supply and demand in the gas grid. The booster station has a gas compressor that can deliver the flow from a low pressure pipeline to a high pressure pipeline, for example between DSO and TSO or in some cases between two DSO pressure levels. When there is over production of local feeders in the network, DSOs don't need to shut down the feeder in order to maintain the pipeline pressure. The excess supply can be transferred to a higher pressure network that has larger demand capacity.

Figure 5 WOS deliver the hydrogen from TSO grid to DSO grid (left). Booster station deliver flow from low pressure network to high pressure network (right).
 Image source: Enexis

D. Curtailment

In some cases, other control strategies may not be able to increase the capacity of the gas network. This usually happens if the pressure is increased and the upper pressure limit of the grid is reached. Then, the operator is forced to limit the feed-in of the gas, this is called curtailment. By allowing less feed-in flow or even shutting down a feeder, the pressure of the network is maintained within the allowable limits. This action is the last option for the operator as each feeder has a contract for feeding in the network at usually constant flow rate. Curtailing the feeder is costly.

3.2 Case study

Two networks were provided by the DSO partners Enexis and Liander, as case studies. The networks are only a part of the two DSO's jurisdiction. The networks were imported to the Aurora simulator and scenarios were defined for each network to answer the research questions. Then, the scenarios were simulated with each network and the results were analysed. A detailed description of each network follows in the following sections.

3.2.1 Uden-Mill

Network description

Figure 6 The ENEXIS distribution network case study. The 8 bar pipelines in the areas of Uden, Mill, Boekel, Boxmeer and Oploo are included in this case study. The pipelines are illustrated with red lines, the supply stations with green squares and the aggregated consumer clusters (or District Station) with blue triangles.

A part of the distribution network was selected by the DSO Enexis for the first case study. The network includes the towns of Uden, Mill, Boekel, Boxmeer and Oploo. In Figure 6, the network is illustrated. The figure shows the layout of the 8 bar pipelines, the supply station locations, and the demands. In the Uden-Mill network, District Stations are treated as demands. This means that at each demand location shown in the figure is a cumulative flow of several houses and it is considered as a flow boundary. Pipelines connect the five towns with a relatively simple path. A single pipeline connects the neighbouring towns and pipeline branches reach the neighbourhoods in each town. In the towns of Uden, Mill and Boxmeer ring loop pipelines also exist, which increase the complexity of the network. A GOS (*Gas Ontvang Station*), which is the connection to the high-pressure transportation network, is found in each one of the five towns. Additionally, three green gas feeders are planned for this distribution network. For the purpose of this study the green gas feeders are simulated as pure hydrogen feeders.

Table 3 List of assets included in the Uden-Mill case study network.

#	Asset type	Asset name	Parameters
1	Supply	GOS Boekel	Pressure setpoint = 8.0/7.0 bar
2		GOS Uden	Pressure setpoint = 7.5/7.0 bar
3		GOS Mill	Pressure setpoint = 7.5/7.0 bar
4		GOS Boxmeer	Pressure setpoint = 7.5/7.0 bar
5		GOS Oploo	Pressure setpoint = 8.0/7.0 bar
6		Green gas/Hydrogen feeder 1	Natural gas (NG) flow setpoint = 1500 Nm ³ /h
7		Green gas/Hydrogen feeder 2	NG flow setpoint = 2300 Nm ³ /h
8		Green gas/Hydrogen feeder 3	NG flow setpoint = 1000 Nm ³ /h
9	Pipelines		3300 pipe sections Total length = 159 km
10	Nodes		3265 nodes
11	Demand		290 District Stations Total NG flow = 77637 Nm ³ /h (-13°C situation)

The assets from the Uden-Mill network are listed on Table 3. As it was explained, there are eight suppliers in total. Five of them are the GOS stations. The GOS suppliers have a pressure setpoint. The setpoint value is different for the summer and winter periods. During the winter, the GOS suppliers in Uden, Mill and Boxmeer have a pressure setpoint of 7.5 bar and the GOS suppliers in Boekel and Oploo have a pressure setpoint of 8 bar. During the summer, all the GOS have a pressure setpoint of 7.0 bar. The lowered pressure setpoint values aim to allow the feeders to feed-in during the summer, when the demand is usually lower. These pressure setpoints are given by Enexis as starting condition.

Green gas feeders

The green gas feeders have a flow setpoint boundary condition. In contrast with the GOS stations where having a fixed setpoint pressure, the feeders' pressure depends on pressure drop (flow dependent) in the network. A green gas feeder has a constant flow unless the pressure is greater or equal to the setpoint pressure. The setpoint pressure at the feeders is 8 bar. In the occasion where the demand is low, the flow rates in the pipelines and consequently the pressure drop is lower. As a result, the pressure at the feeder outlet is increasing until it reaches 8 bar. Then the feeder is shut down. This simulates the scenario where the green gas feeder has a contract with the DSO operator, where the feeding flow rate is always fixed. Therefore, if the pressure distribution allows, the green gas feeders have a constant flow rate, and the remaining demand is provided by the GOS suppliers. Feeder 1 has a (Natural Gas) flow setpoint of 1500 Nm³/h, feeder 2 has a flow setpoint of 2300 Nm³/h and feeder 3 has a flow setpoint of 1000 Nm³/h. The combined feed-in natural gas flow capacity is 4800 Nm³/h.

Measured GOS flow

Figure 7 The total natural gas flow rate at the five GOS stations. Peak flow rate occurs on 15th of December at 9 o'clock in the morning, with a value of 43878 Nm³/h.

Measured flow rate values of natural gas at the GOS stations were provided by Enexis for one year. In Figure 7, we observe the sum of all five GOS flows for year 2022. The values vary during the year with the lowest value in August and the highest value in December. The peak total GOS flow and thus the peak total demand occurs at 9:00 am on December 15th, at 43878 Nm³/h. From Figure 8, it is observed that the measurements indicate a periodic variation of the total flow rate every 24 hours, with increased flow rates during the day and decreased flow rates during the night.

Figure 8 Total GOS flow of natural gas, winter week

GOS flow profile as demand flow boundary

For the purposes of the current study, the total GOS flow rate values were repurposed as an input hourly profile at the demands since there is no green gas feeder yet in measurement data year 2022. All the three green gas feeders are planned. The total GOS flow profile from Figure 7 was normalised, so the maximum value is equal to 1. Additionally, a ratio of each demand to the total demand was

calculated for the -13 °C scenario. The -13 °C scenario is the worst-case scenario calculated by Enexis based on all connections in the Uden/Mill grid. This value represents the maximum natural gas demand of the coldest day in a year. Enexis provided the maximum demand values for all 290 substations in 2022. The maximum demand flow rate is equal to 77637 Nm³/h of natural gas at the -13 °C scenario.

For running the scenarios of Uden-Mill, the hourly demand flow profiles are required. To obtain the hourly flow profile at each demand, the given demand value was multiplied with the ratio of the real peak measured GOS flow and the maximum flow at -13 °C scenario. Then, multiplied by the normalised GOS profile to get the actual hourly demand profile per demand.

Figure 9 Comparison of simulated and measured flow rates at the GOS of Boekel, Uden, Mill, Boxmeer and Oploo towns. The dashed lines show the measured values, and the solid lines show the simulated values with the Aurora simulator.

As a check, the natural gas scenario was simulated with Aurora and the simulated flow rates at the five GOS were compared to the measured flow rates provided by Enexis. The comparison is illustrated with Figure 9. The comparison of the simulated and measured flow rates confirms, that repurposing the GOS flow rates as a demand flow boundary, gives a good approximation of the flow distribution in the network of Uden-Mill even though there is still a mismatch; under predicted flow in Boxmeer area and over predicted in Oploo area. In order to improve the matching, the flow measurements at District Stations would be needed.

Hydrogen as a gas

Since the scope of the current project includes the investigation of future scenarios with 100% hydrogen distribution from the DSOs, the natural gas flow rates were translated to hydrogen flow rates. The first step was to multiply the measured values with a factor of 3 to approximate the flow rates of hydrogen for the same energy flow at the measured GOS stations. The factor is the energy density ratio of natural gas over hydrogen, and it is calculated with the equation given below.

$$\frac{NG}{H_2} \text{ energy density ratio} = \frac{HHV_{NG} * \rho_{NG}}{HHV_{H_2} * \rho_{H_2}} = \frac{42.2 \frac{MJ}{kg} * 0.833 \frac{kg}{m^3}}{141 \frac{MJ}{kg} * 0.08988 \frac{kg}{m^3}} = 2.8 \approx 3$$

where HHV is the higher heating value in $\frac{MJ}{kg}$ and ρ is the density in $\frac{kg}{m^3}$ of the gases.

The flow rate and pressure distribution in the Uden-Mill network is illustrated with Figure 10 and Figure 11. Hour 09:00, on day 15th of December is plotted, at which the demand flow rate peaked for the given year. For this case, we assume no hydrogen supply at the original green gas supply locations. So all supply is coming from the WOS (*Waterstof Ontvangst Station*) stations only.

Figure 10 Reference simulation of a winter day, pipe flow rate results at 15/12 09:00. At this hour, the highest demand flow rates occurred in one year.

In Figure 10, the flow rate of hydrogen through the pipelines is plotted. Flow is higher at the pipes coming from the WOS stations and lower at the branches far away from the stations. The WOS with the highest flow rate is the Uden station. The flow rate values from the WOS stations are given below:

- WOS Uden: 46634 Nm³/h
- WOS Boekel: 22209 Nm³/h
- WOS Boxmeer: 18864 Nm³/h
- WOS Mill: 15981 Nm³/h
- WOS Oploo: 14649 Nm³/h

Figure 11 Reference simulation of a winter day, node pressure results at 15/12 09:00. At this hour, the highest demand flow rates occurred in one year. The yellow star indicates the location with the lowest pressure value, at 6.996 bar.

As it was explained earlier, during the winter, the WOS have the following pressure setpoints:

- WOS Uden: 7.5 bar
- WOS Boekel: 8.0 bar
- WOS Boxmeer: 7.5 bar
- WOS Mill: 7.5 bar
- WOS Oploo: 8 bar

The pressure distribution is illustrated in Figure 11. It is observed that at the WOS locations the pressure is equal to the setpoint values. The pressure is decreasing with the distance from the WOS. The nodes furthest from the stations are at the lowest pressures. The lowest pressure in the network is observed at the end of the branches which are supplied by Uden, Mill and Boxmeer WOS. This was expected as these WOS have the lower pressure setpoint. Overall, the lower pressure is 6.996 bar it is observed North-West of Uden, indicated with a yellow star.

Comparing the real natural gas flow and the fictive hydrogen scenario, we arrive at a few preliminary conclusions. The pressure drops in the pipelines are similar, thus the pressure levels in the network are similar, only with some marginal differences. The differences may be due to the approximation of the Hydrogen-to-Natural gas energy density ratio. Additionally, the flow rates and therefore the flow velocities are significantly increased in the pipelines, with a factor of approximately 3, as it is explained. In the future gas networks with hydrogen, the increased flow rates and flow velocities may cause some problems [9]. For example, vibration or noise can be included in some cases, something which is out of the scope of the current study.

Imbalance of feed-in and demand in a year

Figure 12 The orange line illustrates the Uden-Mill demand flow rate values in a year as a function of the number of hours. The orange line illustrates the feed-in flow rate for the 3 hydrogen feeders in the Uden-Mill network. The red cross shows the point where the two lines coincide.

A study to determine the number of hours with imbalance in a year is carried out. With imbalance we mean the hours where the total feed-in flow rate at the hydrogen feeders is greater than the total flow demand in the Uden-Mill network. To obtain the number of hours the total demand flow rate is obtained and sorted from high to low. The result is illustrated with the blue line in Figure 12. With the orange line, the total hydrogen flow rate at the feeders is illustrated, which also happens to be constant.

We can then observe that for 31% of the hour timesteps, the feed-in flow rate of hydrogen at the feeders is greater than the total demand flow rate. The percentage is significant, and it requires action to prevent this imbalance. This is why we investigate the network of Uden-Mill with the given assumptions. On the other hand, it is up to the operator to decide a balancing strategy for each distribution network.

3.2.2 H2avennet Network description

Figure 13 The H2avennet of Liander distribution network case study. The planned 16 bar pipelines in Amsterdam, geometry of the grid has been altered to keep the location undisclosed. The pipelines are illustrated with red lines, the supply assets with green squares and the industrial consumers with blue triangles.

The DSO Liander provided the distribution network illustrated with Figure 13. The network is drawn in a simple way as it is still under development and the final asset locations and pipeline path is not defined. The pipeline lengths, diameters and locations of the assets represents a good approximation of the future network.

In the network there are three import stations, Imports 1, 2 and 3, one of which is the connection to the high-pressure transportation network (Import 1), and it is also called TSO with capacity 200 MW_{H2}. Imports 2 and 3 will be hydrogen supply that is imported (with capacity 75 MW_{H2} and 100 MW_{H2} respectively), for example by ship. For the purposes of the current study, all three imports are assumed to be flexible and modelled with a pressure boundary condition. This means that at the imports the

pressure is fixed, and it is assumed that the import can react to the hydrogen demand profile. Additionally, gas is supplied by a biomass gasification feeder with 7.4 MW_{H2} capacity and Electrolyser 1 with 200 MW_e capacity.

In the network, the hydrogen is supplied to 9 demands. Three demands are industries that consume hydrogen as a feedstock and six demands are industries that require hydrogen to produce heat. The pipeline network has simple branch connections and does not include ring loops. A list of the H2avennet network assets is given with Table 4, where all flows are for hydrogen. The flow capacity values on the table are estimations for the future since the network is still under development.

Table 4 List of assets included in the H2avennet case study network. The capacities of the assets are not yet fixed, as they are plans for the future situation in the H2avennet network.

#	Asset type	Asset name	Parameters
1	Supply	Import 1 (TSO, 200 MW _{H2})	Pressure setpoint = 15 bar. Max flow = 71642 Nm ³ /h
2		Import 2 (75 MW _{H2})	Pressure setpoint = 15 bar. Max flow = 26866 Nm ³ /h
3		Import 3 (100 MW _{H2})	Pressure setpoint = 15 bar. Max flow = 35821 Nm ³ /h
4		Biomass gasification feeder (7.4 MW _{H2})	Max flow = 2651 Nm ³ /h
5		Electrolyser 1 (200 MW _e)	Max flow = 42985 Nm ³ /h
6	Demand	Feedstock consumer 1 (34.75 MW _{H2})	Max flow = 12448 Nm ³ /h
7		Feedstock consumer 2 (44.7 MW _{H2})	Max flow = 16012 Nm ³ /h
8		Feedstock consumer 3 (22.35 MW _{H2})	Max flow = 8006 Nm ³ /h
9		Heat consumer 1 (17.21 MW _{H2})	Max flow = 6166 Nm ³ /h
10		Heat consumer 2 (8.16 MW _{H2})	Max flow = 2923 Nm ³ /h
11		Heat consumer 3 (18 MW _{H2})	Max flow = 6448 Nm ³ /h
12		Heat consumer 4 (3.1 MW _{H2})	Max flow = 1110 Nm ³ /h
13		Heat consumer 5 (30 MW _{H2})	Max flow = 10746 Nm ³ /h
14	Heat consumer 6 (55 MW _{H2})	Max flow = 19701 Nm ³ /h	
15	Pipelines		21 pipe sections Total length = 19.42 km
16	Nodes		22 nodes

Biomass gasification feeder

Figure 14 Biomass gasification feed-in hourly profile.

The biomass gasification feeder is operated with flow boundary condition. It has capacity of 7.4 MW_{H₂}. The feed-in flow profile of the feeder is illustrated with Figure 14. As it can be observed, the biomass gasification feeder has a constant flow of 2651 Nm³/h with occasional instances with zero flows or downtime. The downtime instances represent maintenance or not operational of the feeder.

Electrolyser

For the electrolyser, it is assumed that it is supplied with power produced at an offshore wind park Hollandse Kust Zuid (HKZ) or Hollandse Kust Noord (HKN). Thus, the electrolyser is operated with a flow boundary condition, and it follows the wind speed profile converted to wind power using wind power curve of 8 MW wind turbine (Figure 15) with total capacity 200 MW (25 wind turbines). The feed-in flow output of the electrolyser is calculated from electrolyzer power-flow curve (Figure 16), that has maximum flow 42985 Nm³/h at 200 MW_e. This is based on alkaline electrolyzer as specified in Table 5, later the electrolyzer pressure will be increased to the grid pressure with a compressor to 16 bar. The wind profile is obtained from the KNMI data platform [10]. The flow profile used as a boundary condition for the grid at the electrolyser outlet is illustrated with Figure 17.

Figure 15 Wind power curve of 8 MW wind turbine

Figure 16 Electrolyzer power-flow curve (left) and specific energy consumed (right) to convert electricity power input to hydrogen output

Table 5 Specification properties of 200 MW alkaline electrolyzer

Operational parameters	Value
Operating pressure	1 bar
Specific Energy	55 kWh/kg H ₂
Current density range	[0, 0.72] A/cm ²
Operating temperature	80 °C
Capacity	200 MW
Minimum load	20%

Figure 17 Electrolyser feed-in hydrogen flow profile based on wind power curve and electrolyzer power-flow curve generated from wind speed profile of 200 MW wind farm HKN or HKZ area.

Hydrogen demand

The feedstock and heat consumers in the H2avennet network have a flow boundary condition. Liander provided with the flow profiles for the consumers. The feedstock consumer profiles are illustrated with Figure 18 and the heat consumers profiles are illustrated with Figure 19. The feedstock consumers are industrial consumers with a constant flow demand. At a few instances the demand goes to zero, which represents downtime of the respective industry due to maintenance or failure. Similarly, heat consumers 1, 2, 3 and 4 have a constant flow demand with downtime at a few instances. Heat consumers 5 and 6 have a more random flow demand with a lot of downtime and occasionally demand

peaks of various amplitudes. This flow demand can also be an industrial user of hydrogen, but with different contract due to the industry’s nature.

Figure 18 Feedstock consumers flow profiles.

Figure 19 Heat consumers flow profiles.

Hydrogen simulations

An initial description of the hydrogen simulations of H2avennet network is given in this section. The network was simulated with the static solver in a winter day. A snapshot of the pressure distribution and flow at the pipelines is illustrated with the figures below.

Figure 20 Static simulation results of scenario A for the H2avennet network. Snapshot of pressure values on 03/02 at 10:00.

In Figure 20 we can observe a snapshot of pressure results at the pipelines. For this scenario, the pressure is higher in the area close by the electrolyser, which is located on the East side of the network. The highest pressure on 03/02 at 10:00 is 15.06 bar and the lowest pressure is 15 bar near location of Import 2. We don't see any significant pressure drop in the system, it means that the current pipeline diameter is oversized compared to the total demand flow.

Figure 21 Static simulation results of scenario A for the H2avennet network. Snapshot of flow values on 3 Feb at 10:00.

In Figure 21 we can observe a snapshot of flow rate results at the pipelines. The flow rate is higher at the East side of the network, at the pipes which are directly connected to the electrolyser. The observed maximum flow rate value in a pipe is 43297 Nm³/h.

Imbalance of feed-in and demand in a year

Similarly to the previous case study, we also look into the imbalance of feed-in flow rate and demand flow rate for one year.

Figure 22 Total demand and feed-in flow rates in the H2avennet network for one year. Total feed-in flow rate is illustrated with the orange line and total demand flow rate is illustrated with the blue line.

For the H2avennet network the feed-in flow rate is dependent on the weather and more specifically on the wind velocity profile. Therefore, it is not constant. The feed-in flow rates and demand flow rates are summed up and illustrated with Figure 22, with two separate curves. The difference of the two values gives us the balance between the two values. The result values are sorted from high to low and presented with Figure 23.

Figure 23 Feed-in and demand flow rate difference in the H2avennet network, with sorted values from high to low.

In Figure 23 the negative values represent the hours of the year with imbalance. With negative imbalance we mean that the feed-in flow rate is higher than the demand flow rate. For the H2avennet case study, imbalance is observed for 1.43% of the hour timesteps in one year. H2avennet is a network planned to be realised in the future, thus the flow values are estimations of the expected capacities of the assets. The imbalance percentage is relatively low but the actual percentage may be different.

3.3 Scenarios

The scenarios chosen for each network will be different since the research goals are also different for each case; the combination of scenarios contribute to the overall research questions of this work package. The Uden-Mill network is based on existing natural gas pipelines that could be re-purposed

to hydrogen pipelines, while the H2avennet network is a completely new development of a standalone hydrogen grid. Both networks have different operating pressures, properties and complexity.

The research goals of each network are presented in Table 6 and Table 7 respectively. Since we are not able to answer all the goals within the current scope, the DSOs chose the scenarios from the highest priority (green) to the lowest priority (red) to be investigated.

Priority level

Priority level 1 is higher than number 4. Therefore, we start studying the green scenarios first.

Table 6 List of goals and description for Uden-Mill network

No	Main goal	Description
1	Impact of booster station placement	Where is a good place for placing a booster station? Which parameters may have an impact on it?
2	Impact of outages	a. (with a booster) Will the Waterstof Ontvangst Station (WOS) react quick enough to compensate the loss of gas when a large feeder fails to supply?
3		b. (without a booster) What are the consequences if one, two or three feeders simultaneously fail. How is the dynamic pressure over the time?
4	Feeder priority based on pressure control	Can we, by giving single static pressure settings to the stations, WOS and feeders, give a priority to a feeder in the entire summer days (low demand)?
5		What will be the impact of adding a booster station on this priority pressure settings?
6	Impact of dynamic pressure management for extra capacity	How much more capacity can we create by having a dynamic pressure management system in the WOS and high pressure network of this region?
7		How to dynamically control the pressure at the gas feeder to increase the feed-in flow limit and increase the uptime of the gas feeder?

Table 7 List of main goal and description for H2avennet network

No	Main Goal	Description
1	Balance between demand vs supply	How does the grid dynamically respond to different demand-supply scenarios?
2	Impact of renewables (sun and wind) availability	What are the consequences if one or more feeders production are dependent on weather conditions (e.g. availability of sun and wind) and therefore has a variable simultaneous production.
3	New feeder placement	Where could we admit a new importer at current configurations?
4	Security of supply and priority arrangement	What will be a good minimum pressure setting in the WOS (summer setting)? With steady input, with varying input and how to determine it?

5	through pressure management or flow management	Should one manage by pressure or should one manage by the gas flow with aim to ensure security of supply? Considering the importers should not influence each other.
6	Impact of one feeder capacity changes	What happens if an importer starts to import more because the contract changes and is therefore extended?

3.3.1 Uden-Mill scenarios

Based on the priority list given in the previous section, we initially start with two scenarios for the Uden-Mill case: understanding the impact of outages of the hydrogen feeder and how to prioritize the hydrogen feeder based on static pressure settings.

A. Impact of outages

All DSOs use a static solver in their gas network modelling tool. Currently, they are not able to simulate the transient behaviour of the network, like what is happening to the pressure dynamics of the system when suddenly there is a sudden change of the hydrogen feeder (failure). To investigate this scenario, we are investigating the settings below:

- Time range: winter season (3 days with the highest demand)
- Setpoint pressure of two WOS (Boekel and Oploo) are at 8 bar and three WOS (Uden, Mill, Boxmeer) are at 7.5 bar
- Three hydrogen feeders with a constant flowrate of 4500, 6900, and 3000 Nm³/h respectively and setpoint pressure at 8 bar.
- Minimum pipeline pressure is 6 bar and the maximum is 8 bar.
- Sudden shut-down of hydrogen feeders:
 - Day 1: three feeders shut-down between 08:00-16:00
 - Day 2: two feeders shut-down between 08:00-16:00
 - Day 3: one feeders shut-down between 08:00-16:00
- WOS is able to compensate the losses gas when the feeder fails (instantaneous or with delay, e.g. 15 minutes)

B. Feeder priority based on pressure control

During the low demand season (summer), the pressure drop in the network is not as high as in the winter season. There are some moments where the pressure at the output of a hydrogen feeder is higher than the setpoint pressure. When this event happens, the hydrogen feeder is not able to deliver the flowrate according to the contract or is closed due to lockup pressure (the pressure is above the setpoint pressure of the feeder). Based on year 2022, there were 2742 hours (31%) that the total demand is lower than total feeders' contract. We aim to find the setpoint pressure of WOS and hydrogen feeders to give priority for the first hydrogen feeders (the priority is based on first-come-first-serve basis) for the following scenario settings:

- Time range: summer season (three days with the lowest demand)
- Maximum two setpoint pressure changes in the summer for WOS and hydrogen feeders
- Minimum pipeline pressure is 6 bar and the maximum is 8 bar.
- Hydrogen feeders flowrate will be adjusted when the pressure is higher than setpoint pressure.

- Feeder priority as follows: Feeder 1 (high), Feeder 2 (medium) and Feeder 3 (low).

C. Booster placement

Booster installation will help the hydrogen feeders continuous supply to the grid in line with the contract. In case that the total supply is higher than the total demand, the feeder will deliver the gas to a higher-pressure pipeline (TSO network). This scenario aims to find and determine the best location for placing booster.

- Time range: summer season (three days with the lowest demand) and total demand < total feeders contract
- Only one booster can be deployed in the network
- Booster will be installed next to WOS.
- Minimum pipeline pressure is 6 bar and the maximum is 8 bar.

3.3.2 H2avennet scenarios

H2avennet is a standalone hydrogen network that in future will be connected to the backbone grid of the TSO. Therefore, the main question is: how can we achieve balance between supply and demand, while the pipeline pressure remains within acceptable pressure limits.

A. Impact of renewables availability (feeder capacity change)

Hydrogen is supplied from both imports and the electrolyzer. The electrolyzer uses a weather-dependent renewable energy source, which is the wind, thus the hydrogen production is intermittent. The parameters that describe scenario A are listed below:

- Time range: 7 days simulation.
- 1 electrolyzer with flow capacity which follows the wind speed profile.
- 1 biomass gasification feeder with given production profile.
- 2 hydrogen imports with a pressure setpoint of 15 bar. This planned setpoint is coming from DSO.
- No connection to the TSO network.
- Minimum pipeline pressure is 10 bar and the maximum is 16 bar.

B. Additional feeder placement (sun)

This scenario investigates the optimal location of an additional hydrogen feeder. Scenario A is assumed as the basis with the addition of an extra hydrogen feeder. The additional feeder is modelled as a 50 MW_e electrolyser with max 10746 Nm³/h flow capacity, which is powered by a solar park. The grid feed-in flow of the additional electrolyser is therefore following the solar irradiance profile and scaled to Nm³/h.

Figure 24 Normalised solar irradiance timeseries values of one year, from the KNMI data platform [10].

Figure 25 Normalised solar irradiance timeseries values. The data are the same as in Figure 24, narrowed down to the simulation period of scenario B, 3 Feb to 10 Feb.

The solar irradiance data of last year are retrieved from the KNMI database website and normalised. The normalised data are illustrated with Figure 24. For scenario B, the period 3 Feb to 10 Feb is simulated. We choose this period to have a similar time range for comparison with Scenario A. The solar irradiance profile during this period is illustrated with Figure 25.

Figure 26 H2avenet network with additional electrolyser. Suppliers are illustrated with light green squares, demands with blue triangles and the potential locations for the additional electrolyser with dark green squares.

The potential locations for the additional electrolyser are illustrated in Figure 26. Location 1 is at the location where Import 1 (TSO) was originally located. Location 2 is at the end of the pipeline branch that

is in the North of the network. Location 3 is at the East part of the network, on the right side of the existing Electrolyser 1.

The parameters from scenario A apply to the current scenario. The additional parameters are listed below:

- Time range: 7 days simulation.
- Additional 1 electrolyzer with capacity 50 MW_e based on sun profile.
- Location of the additional hydrogen feeder: 3 possible locations are examined.
- Minimum pipeline pressure is 10 bar and the maximum is 16 bar.

3.4 Simulation Results and Discussion

This section will provide the simulation results based on scenarios defined in the previous section for both Uden-Mill and H2avennet case. Every simulated scenario will include observation, discussion and conclusion. Overall conclusions of the investigations will be presented in Chapter 4.

3.4.1 Uden-Mill simulation results

For Uden-Mill we investigate three cases:

- A) Impact of outages
- B) Priority of feeders
- C) Possible location for a booster

A. Impact of outages

The simulation is using the converted flow profile data from 14-12-2022 to 17-12-2022 (Figure 27). In this period, it covers the highest flowrate during the year that will lead to the highest pressure drop in the network.

Figure 27 Converted hydrogen flowrate from natural gas GOS measurement

During this period, the hydrogen feeders are having planned maintenance with combinations as shown in Figure 28. In the 1st day, all 3 feeders are shut down, followed by the 2nd day where 2 feeders are shut down and the 3rd day where only 1 feeder is shut down.

Figure 28 Hydrogen feeder planned maintenance schedule

We will run 2 analyses, the 1st analysis uses a static gas network solver to understand the pressure and flow distribution in the network and the 2nd analysis uses a transient gas network solver to understand the dynamic pressure changes of the network due to sudden change in the hydrogen feeder flow.

Static Analysis

The static simulation is done for a duration of 3 days with hourly time step. The results show the lowest pressure in the 8 bar pipeline is 6.79 bar (Figure 29). This occurs during the highest demand in the year 2022 and still above the 6 bar minimum pressure limit. It means that the pressure settings of the WOS are still acceptable. These pressure settings come from the -13 °C scenario.

Figure 29 Network pressure distribution during the highest demand on 15 December 2022. The lowest pressure in the 8 bar pipeline is 6.79 bar

The flow and pressure results for the static analysis of the WOS and hydrogen feeder are shown in Figure 30 and Figure 31 respectively. We can see that the hydrogen feeder flow rate is zero between 8 am to 4 pm. All three hydrogen feeders have a pressure below their setpoint pressure of 8 bar, thus the hydrogen feeder is able to supply the hydrogen based on contract. All three hydrogen feeders are located in the same city near WOS Mill, thus the WOS flowrate is low when the hydrogen feeders are operated and WOS flowrate is high during maintenance period of hydrogen feeder.

Figure 30 Static flowrate at WOS and hydrogen feeder for 3 days simulation with 1-hour timestep.

When the hydrogen feeder is on operation, the pressure is higher than 7.5 bar (setpoint nearest WOS) in order to deliver the flow to the network. During the maintenance period, since there is no flow from the hydrogen feeders, the pressure downstream of the hydrogen feeder is lower than the nearest WOS pressure.

Figure 31 Static pressure at WOS and hydrogen feeder for 3 days simulation with 1 hour timestep.

Transient Analysis

We have shown the static simulation results in the previous section. Now, we would like to see the impact in dynamic pressure when there is a sudden change of flow at the hydrogen feeders. We will focus on December 14th where 3 feeders are shut down. To answer this, we use the transient solver. The transient simulation will use 1-minute timestep or lower than the settling time of the system. We run 2 different simulations: a.) WOS is able to response immediately when the event occurs, b.) WOS react to the change with a certain delay (e.g. 15 minutes).

Figure 32 shows the change of pressure and flow downstream of WOS and hydrogen feeders. It requires around 5-6 minutes to reach the settling time, thus our previous static analysis for hourly timestep is valid since the dynamics in the system has gone after several minutes.

Figure 32 The flow (top) and pressure (bottom) dynamic change of the WOS and hydrogen feeder when there is maintenance at 8 am and WOS able to response immediately.

When we look closely, the total flow going-in and going-out the network is not the same during the transition period (Figure 33). Since the gas is a compressible, the mass imbalance during the transient is covered by the line-pack capacity.

Figure 33 Total flow going in and going out from the network when the WOS response immediately.

Now, the next simulation will show what happens if the WOS does not react immediately to the flow changes from the hydrogen feeders. We introduce 15 minutes delay for each WOS and maintain constant flowrate of WOS. As shown in Figure 34, the pressure drops to around 4 bar at WOS Uden, Mill, and Boxmeer in the first 15 minutes due to high imbalance (~29 kNm³/h) in the network and the lowest pressure in the system is 3.45 bar at 8:14 am. Then WOS start to recover the pipeline pressure to the desired setpoint pressure by introducing a high flow (~300 kNm³/h) from the TSO network (Figure 36). This scenario is chosen to give insight what happens if the regulator valve does not act as

intended, e.g. valve stuck, etc. Since, we don't have any information about maximum capacity of WOS, thus we don't limit the flowrate from the WOS.

Figure 34 The flow (top) and pressure (bottom) dynamic change of the WOS and hydrogen feeder when there is maintenance at 8 am and WOS not able to respond immediately, with a delay of 15 minutes.

Figure 35 Pressure distribution at 8:14 am before the WOS recovers the pressure loss.

Figure 36 shows that the settling time of the pressure recovery takes less than 10 minutes. Note: we don't limit the flowrate coming from these 5 WOS. This settling time could take a longer time if we introduce flowrate limit at WOS.

Figure 36 Total flow going in and going out from the network when the WOS response with 15 minutes delay.

Conclusion on impact of outages

From combination both static and dynamic analysis, we are able to design what is the pressure requirements for WOS in order to have a stable and safe operation over the year. The static analysis can be used to determine the design pressure of each inlet point of the network (WOS and hydrogen feeder) by using either -13 °C scenario (maximum demand) or using actual measurements from previous years with some statistics to have more optimal design.

The transient analysis can complement the static design by introducing additional scenario w.r.t failure, system dynamics, etc. These transient results will give more info about what to do in case the system does not follow the system normal operating conditions. It will set additional criteria when designing pressure requirements (e.g., response time, rise time, settling time, overshoot, tolerance band, etc.) as shown in Figure 37.

Figure 37 An illustration of how system reacts with a changing setpoint input.

B. Feeder priority based on pressure control

In the gas network, both WOS and hydrogen feeder are output pressure regulated. The priority of the producer is determined by the setpoint pressure of each producer. Even though pressure regulated, the hydrogen feeder has special characteristics to run following a setpoint flowrate from the process. In the case of green gas feeder, the flowrate is mainly constant based on contract and in the case of hydrogen feeder, the flowrate is based on electricity generated from renewable energy sources (wind or solar).

The typical pressure regulator curve is shown in Figure 38. In this report, it is assumed that the WOS and the hydrogen feeder have a little droop between low and high flowrate. Both WOS and H₂ feeder is completely shut down when the downstream pressure is higher than setpoint pressure (lockup pressure). The hydrogen feeder will operate in the choked flow regime when the total demand is higher than the total hydrogen feeder. The pressure will be maintained by the WOS setpoint pressure when the WOS provides flow to the grid.

Figure 38 Example operating map of pressure regulator

Supplier pressure management has following steps:

1. Choose the WOS setpoint pressure during winter season (highest demand) and summer season (lowest demand) that satisfies the maximum and minimum pipeline pressure without feeder.
2. When there is an additional feeder in the network next to the WOS, to allow the feeder having a higher priority, the pressure should be above WOS pressure.
3. Redo the step 1 if, with additional feeder, the pipeline pressures stay between maximum and minimum during summer and winter season.
4. To allow feeder priority control in the case of multiple feeders, the setpoint pressure for each feeder needs to be adjusted differently for the summer season.

In the past years, TNO has developed an algorithm to find automatically the setpoint pressure for WOS and hydrogen feeder for prioritization and gas balancing. This algorithm can operate in two modes; dynamically adjusting the setpoint pressure every timestep (point-based optimization) or finding the static setpoint pressure for a period of time (horizon-based optimization).

As reported in [11], currently DSOs do not have remote actuators for controlling the pressure at WOS or feeder and have limited real-time pressure and flow sensors in the network. Thus, implementing

dynamic pressure management is not yet at high priority. In this report we will use TNO horizon-based pressure management optimization to find static pressure for both summer and winter season.

WOS setpoint pressure without hydrogen feeder

The first step is to find the setpoint pressure of the WOS that satisfies the maximum and minimum pipeline pressure. Between January-April and October-December, the hydrogen flow is between 20 kNm³/h (the lowest) and 130 kNm³/h (the highest). And between May-September, the hydrogen demand is between 4 kNm³/h (the lowest) and 40 kNm³/h (the highest), see Figure 39.

Figure 39 Hydrogen demand for one year where it is divided into summer and winter settings

We run simulations for one month in December that covers the flow demand range from 20 to 130 kNm³/h. We define the setpoint pressure at WOS at 7.3 bar. The pressure results at all the District Stations are shown in Figure 40 and the flow distribution results at the WOS are shown in Figure 41.

Figure 40 Pressure distribution at district stations on December 2022. Flow demand between 20 to 130 kNm³/h

Figure 41 Flow distribution at WOS's in December 2022. Flow demand between 20 to 130 kNm³/h

As we can see, when the flow demand is the highest, the minimum pressure in the network is around 6 bar (within pipeline pressure range of 6 to 8 bar). Thus, the initial guess pressure setpoint is already quite good. However, to give additional margin, it is recommended to have WOS's setpoint pressure at 7.5 bar during winter season.

We repeat the analysis for the summer season, we run simulations on June that covers a demand flow range from 5 to 25 kNm³/h. The initial guess pressure of WOS is at 6.2 bar. The results are shown in Figure 42 and Figure 43. The pressure in the network is above the minimum pressure at demand 25 kNm³/h. However, since there is a flow demand between May-September around 40 kNm³/h, it is recommended to put WOS's setpoint pressure minimum at 6.5 bar

Figure 42 Pressure distribution at district stations on June 2022. Flow demand between 5 to 25 kNm³/h

Figure 43 Flow distribution at WOS's on June 2022. Flow demand between 5 to 25 kNm³/h

Hydrogen feeder setpoint pressure during winter season

After finding the required WOS setpoint pressure for the winter season (7.5 bar), we run simulations again with all hydrogen feeders setpoint pressure at 8 bar. The results are shown in Figure 44. The downstream pressure of all hydrogen feeders is below 8 bar, thus the hydrogen feeders are always able to supply to the network in this period when the hydrogen demand is between 60 to 130 kNm³/h. With additional three hydrogen feeders around Mill area, it means that the WOS at Mill has a lower flow compared to the previous results. It happens because the demand in this area is supplied by these feeders.

Figure 44 Flow (top) and pressure (bottom) distribution at WOS (setpoint 7.5 bar) and hydrogen feeder on December 2022. Flow demand between 60 to 130 kNm³/h

However, in April or October, sometimes the demand flowrate can be lower than 40 kNm³/h due to a warm day. Thus, using a setpoint profile of WOS at 7.5 bar will lead to a problem for the hydrogen feeder because the downstream pressure of the hydrogen feeder will be above the setpoint pressure of 8 bar (see Figure 45). When the demand flowrate < 30 kNm³/h, the pressure at the hydrogen feeder 2 will be higher than 8 bar. Thus, this feeder will be closed and not able to supply the gas to the grid.

Figure 45 Flow (top) and pressure (bottom) distribution at WOS (setpoint 7.5 bar) and hydrogen feeder in April 2022. Flow demand between 14 to 40 kNm³/h

The total hydrogen feeders flow contract is 14.4 kNm³/h, thus in order to allow the feeder to be able to supply to the grid, the WOS’s setpoint pressure should be reduced to 6.5 bar. We re-run the simulation and the results are presented in Figure 46.

Figure 46 Flow (top) and pressure (bottom) distribution at WOS (setpoint 6.5 bar) and hydrogen feeder in April 2022. Flow demand between 14 to 40 kNm³/h

If we look back in Figure 39, there are 1330 hours in January to April and October to December where the hydrogen demand flowrate is lower than 30 kNm³/h (or around 30% in winter season). It means that if we use a setpoint pressure of 7.5 bar at WOS, we are not able to have all hydrogen feeders 100% running. We should use WOS's setpoint pressure of 6.5 bar in these hours. Figure 47 shows the minimum pressure at district stations when the WOS's setpoint pressure is at 6.5 bar on March 16th-17th, when the hydrogen demand flowrate is between 35 to 80 kNm³/h. The pressures in this range are above the minimum pipeline pressure and hydrogen feeder pressures are also below 8 bar.

Figure 47 Pressure distribution at district stations in March 2022. Flow demand between 35 to 80 kNm³/h

Because these hours are scattered, it is difficult to determine when we should change the WOS pressure between 7.5 bar and 6.5 bar to allow hydrogen feeders 100% continuous supply and to keep the pipeline pressure between in the maximum and minimum range. The recommended switching points based on flowrate limit are shown in Figure 48. But, this is only working with this 2022's demand profile. Different demand profile in a year will lead different switching strategies.

Figure 48 Minimum hydrogen demand flowrate for WOS's setpoint at 7.5 bar (red dotted line) and maximum hydrogen demand flowrate for WOS's setpoint at 6.5 bar (green dotted line) and the recommended switching point (yellow dotted line)

Hydrogen feeder setpoint pressure for priority control in summer season

In the previous section, we have done analysis about what is the required WOS's setpoint pressure to keep all hydrogen feeders continuous supply. However, in some cases during summer season, it is impossible to do this because the total hydrogen demand is lower than the total of hydrogen feeders' contract. Without the help of a booster station, we need to prioritize the hydrogen feeders by choosing the right setpoint pressure.

When the demand flowrate $< 14.4 \text{ kNm}^3/\text{h}$, the WOS will be closed and the pressure in the network will increase until it reaches the setpoint pressure of hydrogen feeders. The dynamic interaction between WOS and feeder is illustrated in an example with measurements in a DSO gas grid during summer time, as shown in Figure 49. The GOS has a setpoint pressure at 7 bar and green gas feeder at 8.2 bar. In the blue square region, the demand decreases, thus the GOS flow decreases and the network pressures starts to rise. After a couple of hours, the demand increases again, resulting in a pressure decrease of the network and the GOS starts production again. In this measured data, the pressure is never above 8.2 bar, thus the green gas feeder continuously produces. We see that the feeder flow (light green) is slightly reduced during this period and increases again when the demand also increases.

Figure 49 Example measured flowrate (top) and pressure (bottom) of GOS (black) and green gas feeder (green).

In this simulation, we want to show that the priority of the hydrogen feeder can be allocated based on setpoint pressure of the feeder. Hydrogen feeder 1 has the highest priority, followed by feeder 2 and 3. As shown in Figure 46, when the hydrogen demand is around $15 \text{ kNm}^3/\text{h}$, the pressure at feeder 1, 2 and 3 is 7.35, 7.6 and 7.3 respectively. Thus, we set the pressure of feeder 3 at 7.5 bar in order to reduce the flow of feeder 3 first when there is less demand. When the demand is lower than $14.4 \text{ kNm}^3/\text{h}$, then the pipe pressure increases and the feeder 3's pressure hits 7.5 bar. If this happens, the feeder 3's flow will decrease.

We can set both feeders 1 and 2 pressure higher than feeder 3 to have a higher priority. However, we need to put the setpoint pressure of feeder 2 around 0.1 bar lower than feeder 1, to make sure feeder

2 has a lower priority than feeder 1. Thus, setpoint pressure of feeder 1 is at 8 bar and feeder 2 is at 7.9 bar. This delta setpoint pressure (0.1 bar) is chosen with assumption that the regulator valve has a high accuracy within 0.1%. If the accuracy is less, e.g. 1-2%, then we need to take into account the overlap setpoint pressure. Thus, the delta pressure between feeders might be higher than 0.1 bar

We test this setting with a demand profile shown in Figure 50. At 7 pm, the flow demand is lower than the total feeders contract of 14400 kNm³/h. We use the transient solver to investigate the pressure build up when the WOS does not produce to the grid.

Figure 50 Flow demand profile on 1st and 2nd July, to simulate the feeder priority control based on pressure setpoint.

Figure 51 shows the simulation results for WOS and hydrogen feeder’s flow and pressure results on July, 1st. At the start of the simulation, the pressures at WOS Oploo and WOS Boekel are at 6.5 bar because there is still a small flow needed from WOS next to the hydrogen feeders. When the flow demand drops, the pressure starts to increase until it reaches the setpoint pressure of hydrogen feeder 3 at 7.5 bar. When feeder 3’s pressure reaches 7.5 bar, the feeder 3’s flowrate decreases first. Hydrogen feeder 1 and 2 keep flowing according to contract values. The feeder 3’s flow keeps decreasing until 0 and pressures starts to increase above 7.5 bar. When the flow demand drops again which makes the feeder 2’s pressure reaches 7.9 bar and the flowrate decreases following the demand flow. The hydrogen feeder 1 keeps flowing according to contract value. On July 2nd at 7 am the flow demand starts increasing, which makes feeder 2’s flow increasing until reaching the contract and feeder 3’s starts to increase again. And this pressure and flow transient continues.

Figure 51 Flow (top) and pressure (bottom) distribution at WOS (setpoint 6.5 bar) and hydrogen feeder in July 2022. Flow demand between < 15 kNm³/h. Black dotted-line is the setpoint pressure of the feeder.

From the simulation above, it is shown that the priority of the hydrogen feeder can be controlled by adjusting the setpoint pressure. We showed that static pressure management mechanisms can be used to regulate the pressure in the pipeline and can be used for flow balancing.

Conclusion on feeder priority control

Finding setpoint pressures of WOS and hydrogen feeders have several challenges, especially when the networks are complex and having multiple supply points. Either multiple WOS's or hydrogen feeders. The current practice that uses 2 sets of setpoint pressures in a year might not be sufficient when there are additional distributed local feeders in the network. Especially if we want to make sure the feeder has a higher priority than the WOS. We have presented several workflows how to do static pressure management in the network when dynamic pressure management option is not available.

First, we need to design the setpoints pressure to allow high pressure drop during winter season such that it has enough room above the minimum pipeline pressure. Second, we need to design during summer season that the feeder’s pressure stays below the setpoint pressure. Third, if a booster is not an option, then the right choice of setpoint pressures of the feeder is needed to control the prioritization. The hydrogen feeder’s priority currently set based on first come first served basis. Thus feeder 1 has the highest priority compared to feeder 3. We set the feeder with the lowest priority with the lowest setpoint pressure and the feeder with the highest priority with the highest pressure. The summary of setpoint pressures at WOS and feeders are shown in Table 8.

Table 8 Summary of WOS and hydrogen feeders setpoint pressure during different conditions to allow prioritization.

Pressure [bar]	WOS’s	Feeder 1	Feeder 2	Feeder 3
Winter, WOS without feeder	7.5	-	-	-
Summer, WOS without feeder	6.5	-	-	-
Demand > 30 kNm ³ /h	7.5	8	8	8
Demand < 80 kNm ³ /h	6.5	8	8	8
Demand < 14.4 kNm ³ /h	6.5	8	7.9	7.5

C. Booster placement

Introducing a booster station is another solution to keep the hydrogen feeder running continuously based on contract. The booster station is used to deliver flow from the low-pressure network to the high-pressure network. Logically, a booster station is placed closed to the TSO network. In this scenario we will place a booster station next to a WOS.

To keep the hydrogen feeder always running, a booster station is activated when the total demand in the network is lower than total hydrogen feeder contract. The flow imbalance will be delivered back to the high-pressure network. We zoom into the month of August 2022 (Figure 52) where 95.5% of the total hydrogen demand is lower than the total hydrogen feed-in. We will use the time range between 14 August 2022 – 17 August 2022 and place the first booster next to WOS Mill.

Figure 52 Total hydrogen demand and total hydrogen feeder on August 2022

Booster Mill

The booster is used to compensate the imbalance between supply and demand as shown in Figure 53. The total hydrogen demand (orange line) is always lower than the total hydrogen contract value (blue line) in this time range, thus the booster station sends the remainder flow (orange line) to the higher-pressure pipeline. It is assumed that the booster is controlled by monitoring the flow at supply and demand and will operate if the total feeders' flow is higher than the total demand's flow (no flow from WOS).

The pressure drop in the network will be the highest at 15-08-2022 at 1 am when the booster needs to deliver 10.5 kNm³/h.

Figure 53 Flowrate of total hydrogen feeder, total demand and booster during summer period

We set the WOS's pressure at 6.5 bar, lower than the feeder such a way that there is no flow coming from the WOS to the grid (valve is closed due to lockup pressure region), thus the entire hydrogen demand of the grid is supplied by all three hydrogen feeders. The dynamic pressures downstream of the WOS and hydrogen feeders are shown in Figure 54. All the hydrogen feeders have a setpoint pressure at 8 bar, as we can see in the figure that the downstream pressure is below the setpoint pressure, thus all three hydrogen feeders are able to deliver the flow according to the contract. The other way around, the WOS have a setpoint pressure below the downstream pressure of the lowest demand (e.g., 15-08-2022 at 1 am). The WOS is not able to deliver to the grid due to lockup pressure, thus the valve is closed.

Figure 54 Downstream pressure of WOS and hydrogen feeders with a booster station near Mill area.

Figure 55 shows the flow and pressure distribution during the lowest demand (~4 kNm³/h) and the booster is active. The lowest pressure in the system is at 7.6 bar when the setpoint pressure of the hydrogen feeder is at 8 bar. This is located near the booster station of Mill due to pressure drop from the hydrogen feeder.

Figure 55 Flow (top) and pressure (bottom) distribution during the lowest hydrogen demand of the year with a booster station near Mill area (blue square)

Booster Uden

A similar workflow and analysis is repeated for another booster location, now we place the booster near the WOS in Uden area. During the lowest demand hour, the hydrogen feeder needs to deliver ~12.7 kNm³/h to Uden from Mill. Looking at the pressure distribution in the system, it is still higher than the minimum pressure criteria (Figure 56). Thus, it is still possible to place the booster in this area.

Figure 56 Flow (top) and pressure (bottom) distribution during the lowest hydrogen demand of the year with a booster station near Uden area (blue square)

Since the booster is now located in Uden and has some distance from the hydrogen feeder location, the minimum required setpoint pressure for WOS Uden and Boekel, to make sure hydrogen feeder has a higher priority, is found when the booster has a maximum flow (August, 15th at 1 am in Figure 57). While in the Mill area, it is found when the booster has 0 flow (August, 15th at 1 pm in Figure 54).

Figure 57 Downstream pressure of WOS and hydrogen feeders with a booster station near Uden area.

Booster Boxmeer

When the booster station is placed near WOS Boxmeer, the lowest pressure in the network will be below the 6 bar criteria. The lowest pressure in the network is -3.97 bar (becoming unrealistic) because the pipeline diameter connecting Mill and Boxmeer area is too small. It has to deliver 11.6 kNm³/h in this pipe. The flow and pressure distribution are shown in Figure 58. Thus, placing a booster in Boxmeer area is not recommended.

Figure 58 Flow (top) and pressure (bottom) distribution during the lowest hydrogen demand of the year with a booster station near Boxmeer area

Booster Boekel and Oploo

Boekel and Oploo area are even further from the location of the hydrogen feeder, thus the pressure drop results are even worse than Boxmeer and thus also unrealistic. It is because the pipeline connection between the cities is too small. Thus, placing a booster in these two areas is also not recommended. The flow and pressure distribution results are presented in Figure 59 and Figure 60 respectively.

Figure 59 Flow (top) and pressure (bottom) distribution during the lowest hydrogen demand of the year with a booster station near Boekel area

Figure 60 Flow (top) and pressure (bottom) distribution during the lowest hydrogen demand of the year with a booster station near Oploo area

Conclusion on booster location

After running simulations for booster placement in the 5 different locations, we can summarize the results in Table 9. Only 2 places are within the minimum pressure criteria to install a booster station: Mill and Uden. The other 3 areas are having too small pipe diameter connecting between cities to transport the imbalance flow from the hydrogen feeder to the booster station. Resulting in an unrealistic (negative) pressure distribution in the network.

Table 9 Summary of booster placement analysis for different locations in Uden-Mill area.

Booster Location	Mill	Uden	Boxmeer	Boekel	Oploo
Lowest pressure [bar]	7.62	6.54	-3.97	-10.29	-13.21
Status	V	V	X	X	X
Pressure Feeder 1 [bar]	8	8	-	-	-
Pressure Feeder 2 [bar]	8	8	-	-	-
Pressure Feeder 3 [bar]	8	8	-	-	-
Pressure WOS Mill [bar]	< 7.6	< 7.6	-	-	-
Pressure WOS Uden [bar]	< 7.5	< 6.5	-	-	-
Pressure WOS Boxmeer [bar]	< 7.2	< 7.2	-	-	-
Pressure WOS Boekel [bar]	< 7	< 6.5	-	-	-
Pressure WOS Oploo [bar]	< 6.9	< 6.9	-	-	-

The setpoint pressure of the WOS stations is described in such a way that there is no flow coming from the WOS if the hydrogen feeder is able to supply the demand. This setpoint is found by sweeping the minimum downstream pressure at the WOS when the booster has 0 flow (inactive) to the maximum flow (lowest demand). The hydrogen feeder has always a higher priority than the WOS. Due to the booster installation, all hydrogen feeders are able to deliver the flow based on the contract for all the time with a given setpoint pressure. Looking at the table, it is concluded that all WOS's can be set at 6.3 bar and all hydrogen feeders are at 8 bar.

3.4.2 H2avennet simulation results

For H2avennet we investigate two cases:

- A) Impact of renewable energy sources availability
- B) Additional hydrogen feeder placement

A. Impact of renewables availability

Static analysis

Scenario A aims to give insights on how the H2avennet responds to a scenario with variable demand. Electrolyser 1 is modelled in such a way that it simulates the production of hydrogen from wind power. Therefore, the feed-in flow rate of Electrolyser 1 is following the wind speed profile, which is intermittent in time. A winter week is selected for the simulation, with a few days where there is high demand and a few days with low demand. The intermittency of the hydrogen supply is expected to result in times with high supply and low demand and times with low supply and high demand. Times with high demand and low supply will not appear problematic at a first glance since the two Imports can handle the current estimated demand capacity.

Figure 61 Consumers flow demand during the simulation period 03/02-10/02.

The flow demand at the consumers of H2avennet network is illustrated with Figure 61. Total demand between 3 Feb – 7 Feb is 53000 Nm³/h and between 7 Feb – 10 Feb flow demand decreases as low as 27000 Nm³/h.

The static solver of Aurora was employed to obtain the static results of pressure and flow for designing capacity. The static results are expected to provide an overview of the pressure levels over the network and simultaneously an overview of the flow rates at the suppliers. The period of 7 days between 3 Feb – 10 Feb, with a timestep of one hour is simulated. Figures of timeseries results of flow and pressure are presented in this chapter.

Figure 62 Static simulation results of scenario A for H2avennet network. Timeseries results of flow rate, at the suppliers, between 3 Feb – 10 Feb.

Figure 62, illustrates the flow rate results, at the suppliers, as a function of time. During these seven days, Electrolyser 1 supplies hydrogen with the highest flow rate. Specifically, between 3 Feb – 7 Feb, Electrolyser 1 is supplying at maximum capacity for the most amount of time. Furthermore, between 7 Feb – 10 Feb negative flow is observed at Import 2 and Import 3. The negative flow indicates a total flow demand lower than the total supply. In other words, the pre-determined feed-in of the Electrolyser 1 and the Biomass gasification feeder are greater than the total demand during these days.

Figure 63 Static simulation results of scenario A for H2avennet network. Timeseries results of pressure, at the suppliers, between 3 Feb - 10 Feb.

Figure 63 illustrates the pressure results at the suppliers, as a function of time. The pressure setpoint of 15 bar is maintained at Imports 2 and 3 and their pressure curves are overlapping. Pressure at the Biomass gasification feeder is increasing during the periods of feed-in and it is decreasing when it is off. A similar effect is observed at the Electrolyser 1 but at higher pressures as the feed-in flow rate is significantly higher. Between 7 Feb – 10 Feb, when negative flow occurs at Import 2 and Import 3, we observe that the pressure difference between the Electrolyser and the imports is reaching 0.2 bar. This pressure difference is responsible for the negative flows. This negative flow can only be realized if there is a booster compressor in the system. If there is no booster, then we need to curtail the supply.

Curtailment of the electrolyser

A second simulation of scenario A was performed, where Electrolyser 1 is curtailed. The curtailment of Electrolyser 1 means that, at times where we observe negative flow at the imports due to higher supply than demand, the electrolyser’s flow setpoint is decreased. The flow setpoint value of the electrolyser is decreased by the amount of negative flow. Consequently, we observe in Figure 64, that between 07/02-10/02 the flow rate of Electrolyser 1 is following the flow of the demands, which can be seen in Figure 61.

Figure 64 Static simulation results of scenario A for H2avennet network. Timeseries results of flow rate at the suppliers, between 3 Feb – 10 Feb. Scenario A was simulated again, this time curtailing Electrolyser 1, so there are no negative flows at the imports.

Figure 65 Static simulation results of scenario A for H2avennet network. Timeseries results of pressure at the suppliers, between 03/02 - 10/02. Scenario A was simulated again, this time curtailing Electrolyser 1, so there are no negative flows at the imports.

At the same time, we observe that the pressure of the electrolyser is significantly decreased. Comparing the peak pressure value that occur on 9 Feb from Figure 63 and Figure 65, we observe that the pressure is decreased by more than 0.1 bar.

Transient analysis

The transient analysis is performed for scenario A. All the parameters of the scenario are identical to the static analysis. The transient solver of Aurora is employed. The analysis is expected to give a more realistic result of the pressure overview of the H2avennet network, since it can take into account the line packing effect. With line packing we mean the situation where hydrogen is stored in the pipelines by increasing the pressure levels of the pipelines. This occurs when supply is greater than demand.

The time series result for flow and pressure are illustrated below. An estimation of the pressure reaction time in the network is made based on timeseries pressure values at the suppliers.

Figure 66 Transient simulation results of scenario A for the H2avennet network. Flow results at the suppliers between 3 Feb - 10 Feb. The blue arrow shows the point where Electrolyser 1 is restricted because the maximum pressure is reached.

Figure 66 illustrates the flow at the suppliers as a function of time. In contrast with the static results, the time step is 1 minute instead of 60 minutes. The simulation indicates that on 7 Feb at 10:00, the flowrate of Electrolyser 1 is increasing. At this time the maximum pressure of 16 bar is reached, therefore the electrolyser is not allowed to feed-in at a higher flow rate. We can see that the flow rate is capped at approximately 30k Nm³/h. Then on 8 Feb, when the feed-in flow from Biomass gasification feeder is increased, the flow rate at Electrolyser 1 is capped at approximately 27k Nm³/h to maintain a pressure lower than 16 bar.

Figure 67 Simulations results of scenario A for the H2avennet network. Pressure results at the suppliers between 3 Feb – 10 Feb. The blue arrow indicates the time that the network needs to react to a sudden feed-in flow, until the maximum pressure is reached.

With Figure 67, we zoom in at the time when the pressure at Electrolyser 1 reaches the pressure limit of 16 bar. The transient simulation is able to capture the gradual pressure increase due to the sudden increase of flow feed-in from the electrolyser. The time needed for the pressure to reach a steady state is approximately 12 minutes, from 9:59 until 10:11, when there is imbalance around 7000 Nm³/h. Therefore, we suggest that the control system reaction time to a sudden feed-in increase is lower than 12 minutes if we have imbalance around this flowrate or approximate around ~600 kg of hydrogen.

Linepack volume calculation

The transient analysis considers the time dependent effects. A time dependent variable is the gas volume in normal cubic meters (Nm³) which is stored in the network, and it is called line pack. The line pack volume refers to the amount of hydrogen in Nm³ units, that can be stored in the pipelines by increasing the pressure from the minimum allowable pressure to the maximum allowable pressure. Line pack volume for the H2avennet network is calculated with the equation given below, from [12].

$$V_{line\ pack} = V_{geometric} \left[\frac{P_{max}}{Z_{max}} - \frac{P_{min}}{Z_{min}} \right] \cdot \frac{1}{P_{NTP}} \frac{T_{NTP}}{T_{mean}}$$

where

$V_{line\ pack}$ the stored volume of gas at NTP (20 °C and 1 bar). This volume is what we define as line pack volume,

$V_{geometric}$ the geometric volume of pipeline, calculated with the Aurora gas network simulator,

P_{max} the upper pressure limit,

P_{min} the lower pressure limit,

Z_{max} the compressibility factor for pressure = P_{max} ,

Z_{min} the compressibility factor for pressure = P_{min} ,

P_{NTP} the normal pressure,

T_{NTP} the normal temperature,

T_{mean} is the mean operating temperature, normally 15 °C.

Table 10 Linepack calculation.

P_{max}	1.6 MPa (16 bar)
P_{min}	1.0 MPa (10 bar)
Z_{max}	1.00977
Z_{min}	1.00608
P_{NTP}	0.1 MPa (1 bar)
T_{NTP}	293 K (20 °C)
T_{mean}	288 K (15 °C)
$V_{geometric}$	1375 m ³
$V_{linepack}$	8407 Nm ³
Line pack volume per 1 bar pressure increase	~1401 Nm ³ /bar

The calculated values are listed above in Table 10. The calculated line pack volume is 8407 Nm³. This can also be translated to approximately 1401 Nm³ or 125 kg of hydrogen) per 1 bar pressure difference. Therefore, if the network is operating at 15 bar and a surplus flow occurs of 8500 Nm³/h, the pressure will increase to 16 bar in 10 minutes. When the pressure reaches 16 bar the network is then out of the allowable operating conditions, thus the supplier can't inject more to the grid.

Conclusions for scenario A

Results from scenario A simulations highlight a few properties of the H2avennet network.

- The flow rate from an electrolyser that produces hydrogen from wind power can be highly intermittent. In the event of down time at the demands, it is possible for an imbalance of supply-demand to occur.
- Furthermore, due to intermittency of the electrolyser flow, the H2avennet network is not capable of becoming self-sustained. Therefore, it is recommended to the DSO to take action by adding flexibility to the network. Three possible flexibilities are proposed:
 - Connection to TSO network is needed to maintain the security of supply during the times with low wind power or no import. The TSO will supply the network at times with low supply but can't solve the problem of high supply.
 - A booster station can allow the electrolysers to operate at their full potential and supply the surplus hydrogen back to the TSO network. This solution is maximizing the production of the electrolysers and maintains the pressure of the DSO network within the maximum pressure.
 - Add local storage in the DSO network. A storage can take the surplus hydrogen production while maintaining the pressure. Furthermore, the storage can supply the DSO network at times with low wind or solar power, or high demands. This solution also maximizes the production from the electrolysers while maintaining the pressure. If there is seasonal and not daily imbalances in the DSO network, the storage might need to be very big and the cost might not be justifiable.
- The flow of Electrolyser 1 in the static simulation was limited by the demand flow since negative flow is not possible and the flow setpoint of the electrolyser was curtailed.

- The flow of Electrolyser 1 in the transient simulation was limited by the pressure. The electrolyser was also curtailed at the moment when the pressure reached the maximum pressure limit of 16 bar.
- The line pack calculation and the reaction time from the transient analysis indicated that the network could go out of operation (from 15 bar to 16 bar) in about 8-12 minutes for a surplus supply flow of approximately 7000-10000 Nm³/h (or 600-900 kg) of hydrogen. During this time period the operator should take action. Possible actions are the curtailment of the electrolysers, local storage or even a booster station, or flaring of the hydrogen in worst case. This reaction time can be longer if the setpoint pressure is lower, e.g. 13 or 14 bar. Linepack formula in the previous section can give indication how much hydrogen volume imbalance needed in order to increase or decrease pipeline pressure by 1 bar. The reaction time can be calculated by counting the flowrate's duration to achieve this volume (time = volume / flowrate).

B. Additional feeder placement

Static simulations were performed to investigate scenario B for the H2avennet network. A period of 7 days, between 3 Feb – 10 Feb, with a timestep of one hour was simulated. The flow rate and pressure timeseries results are compared between the three locations for the additional feeder.

The static simulation with Aurora is expected to give an indication of possible imbalances in the H2avennet network by placing Electrolyser 2. The imbalances can be a surplus of hydrogen supply. From scenario A, we know that the existing demand in the period 7 Feb – 10 Feb is low and negative flow at the imports is observed. With the addition of Electrolyser 2, we expect more times with oversupply causing negative flows in the model. The impact of the location of Electrolyser 2 should be highlighted by comparing the results.

Additional electrolyser at location 1

Additional electrolyser at location 2

Additional electrolyser at location 3

Figure 68 Static simulation results of scenario B for H2avennet network. Timeseries results of flow rate, at the suppliers, between 3 Feb – 10 Feb. Electrolyser is given in the legend as Electrolyser location 1, 2 or 3.

With Figure 68, the flow rate results for the three possible locations of the additional electrolyser are illustrated. Only the flow rate of Import 2 and Import 3 are influenced by the additional electrolyser. The rest of the suppliers have a pre-defined flow boundary condition. We observe overall similar flow rates from Import 2 and Import 3, relative to scenario A. Between 3 Feb – 7 Feb, locations 1 results in a small negative flow at Import 2. For locations 2 and 3, there is not a negative flow. As expected, between 7 Feb – 10 Feb all locations result to negative flows at Imports 2 and 3.

Additional electrolyser at location 1

Additional electrolyser at location 2

Additional electrolyser at location 3

Figure 69 Static simulation results of scenario B for H2avennet network. Timeseries results of pressure, at the suppliers, between 3 Feb – 10 Feb. Electrolyser 2 is given in the legend as Electrolyser location 1, 2 or 3. For location 3, the red and purple lines coincide between 7 Feb and 10 Feb.

Figure 69 illustrates the pressure results for scenario B. One plot with the suppliers’ pressure is given for each location. The additional electrolyser, Electrolyser 2, at locations 1 and 2 have similar results. Electrolyser 2 has a close to constant pressure at 15 bar, which is the pressure setpoint of Imports 2 and 3. Electrolyser 2 at location 3 has a very different behaviour. The pressure at the electrolyser is significantly higher. Between 3 Feb – 10 Feb it is approximately 15.05 bar. Between 7 Feb – 10 Feb it exceeds 15.2 bar. Location 3 is near the location of Electrolyser 1, thus the pressure at Electrolyser 2 is similar.

Curtailment of the electrolysers

A second set of simulations was performed where negative flow at the imports was prevented by curtailing the electrolysers flow rate. At times where the flow rate becomes negative, the flow setpoint of the additional electrolyser, Electrolyser 2, was decreased first. Then, the flow setpoint of Electrolyser 1 was decreased. The simulations with the curtailment aims to examine the pressures at times when the production is higher that the consumption and the electrolysers need to be curtailed.

Additional electrolyser at location 1

Additional electrolyser at location 2

Additional electrolyser at location 3

Figure 70 Static simulation results of scenario B for H2avennet network, where negative flows are not allowed by curtailing the electrolyzers. Timeseries results of flow rate, at the suppliers, between 3 Feb – 10 Feb. Electrolyser 2 is given in the legend as Electrolyser location 1, 2 or 3.

With Figure 70, the flow results with the three locations of Electrolyser 2 are illustrated. The flow rate of Electrolyser 2 is slightly curtailed between 3 Feb – 7 Feb, at location 1. Between 7 Feb – 10 Feb, Electrolyser 2 is shut down and Electrolyser 1 is curtailed to lower flow rates, to prevent negative flows.

Additional electrolyser at location 1

Additional electrolyser at location 2

Additional electrolyser at location 3

Figure 71 Static simulation results of scenario B for H2avennet network, where negative flows are not allowed by curtailing the electrolysers. Timeseries results of flow rate, at the suppliers, between 3 Feb – 10 Feb. Electrolyser 2 is given in the legend as Electrolyser location 1, 2 or 3.

With Figure 71, the pressure results of scenario B are illustrated. Similarly, to scenario A, the curtailment of the Electrolysers reduced the peak pressures in the network. The pressure now peaks at 15.08 bar on day 7 Feb.

Conclusions from scenario B

- Based on given hydrogen demand and capacity of the suppliers, the standalone network is self-sustainable without having connection to HNS. However, if there is surplus local feeder productions, it needs to be curtailed due to other supplier is not having bidirectional flow.
- The curtailment of the electrolysers decreased the pressures in the network. The peak pressures are decreased by 0.15 bar, to 15.06 bar.
- Location 1, on the West part of the network, is not drastically affecting the pressure. In the West part of the network there are two consumers: Heat consumers 1 and Heat consumer 4, with a total flow demand between 4667-7276 Nm³/h. Electrolyser 2, during times with high solar power can supply the local demands. The simulations showed that the addition of Electrolyser 2 at location 1 is not significantly increasing the pressure.
- Location 2, on the central-North branch of the network, is the location that allows Electrolyser 2 to feed-in at the lowest pressure level. In the central area of the network, the consumers Feedstock consumer 1, Heat consumer 3 and Feedstock consumer 3 have a total flow demand between 22424 – 26902 Nm³/h. As a result, Electrolyser 2 is close from these three demands and therefore it supplies part of the demand flow, up to 10746 Nm³/h. At location 2,

Electrolyser 2 is prioritized over Import 3, which is also located on the North side of the network.

- Location 3, on the East side of the network, Electrolyser 2 is feeding-in at the highest pressure. At this location, Electrolyser 1 and Electrolyser 2 are close to each other. Electrolyser 1 was already supplying the East part of the network and some flow was also going towards the centre of the network. Therefore, the addition of Electrolyser 2 is increasing the pressure in the East part of the network and the flow towards the centre.
- The best location for the additional electrolyser would be location 2, since it is closer to a group of three relatively big consumers and far from the biomass gasification feeder and Electrolyser 1 which has a high flow output. A similar conclusion is obtained for location 1. At location 1, the Electrolyser 2 would be far from electrolyser 1 and biomass gasification feeder, so the pressure is not significantly increasing. Location 1 is further from the big consumers in contrast with location 2.
- In the simulations Electrolyser 2 was curtailed first and then Electrolyser 1 was curtailed if needed. This priority did not allow the pressure to reduce. The inverse priority might have been a best option for reducing the pressure. Curtailing Electrolyser 1 first and placing Electrolyser 2 at locations 1 or 2 is expected to reduce the peak pressure because the feed-in will take place closer to the demands. Therefore, we propose to curtail the feeder which operates at higher pressures first.

4. Conclusions

4.1. Building blocks for a protocol for dynamic feed-in of hydrogen

From a legislative perspective the role of the DSOs is still not fully defined in the current situation, and therefore it is not clear who is responsible for the feed in of hydrogen in the distribution grid and balancing demand and supply. All the different dynamic feed-in strategies have their pros and cons. These issues have been addressed in this report and recommendations have been provided on the possible building blocks for a protocol that describes the dynamic feed-in of hydrogen in future. The following research questions have been addressed:

1. What is the responsibility of DSOs and the procedure for controlling the gas quantities from feeders into their grid?
2. What is the standard procedure to guarantee security of supply of the producer?
3. What is the equipment system needed to monitor and control the producer?

Almost all-important matters that still need to be arranged have to do with the role and responsibilities of the DSOs. The main topics that should be arranged in a future protocol are:

- The roles and responsibilities of the DSOs in relation to third (private) parties like hydrogen producers.
- The responsibility for matching supply and demand and installing the appropriate hardware like buffers. And who decides on the criteria for e.g., pressure for switching off supply or demand.
- A prioritizing scheme is needed for feed-in and/or switching off feeders and it should be made clear who determines the optimal feed-in locations.

In addition to the regulatory aspects that need to be arranged, there is also a need for a document that sets out the practical requirements concerning the feed-in; comparable to the Measuring and Control Protocol ('Beheersprotocol') as is used for biomethane. Main building blocks for this technical document are:

- Requirements of the physical connection to the gas grid
- Description of the measuring equipment and hardware in a 'gate keeper' for hydrogen feed-in.
- Requirements on data communication and data handling. Comparable with the current 'Meetvoorwaarden Gas Regionale Net Beheerders'. It is recommended to use the same demands for hydrogen as now are in use for biomethane.

4.2. Controlling strategies for a network with feed-in

Balancing the supply and demand in the gas network has several challenges when there is additional local feed-in next to the GOS in the network. This already has direct impact to DSOs when they have new requests from local producers to have a new connection of green gas feeder to the grid. They need to decide what is the best fitted flow contract for the green gas feeder and to facilitate maximum uptime.

The future hydrogen network will face similar challenges, it is mainly due to more distributed local feeders and the intermittent supply of hydrogen from renewable energy sources like solar and wind. When there is imbalance in the network, the grid pressure will increase or decrease. The objective of the grid management is to control the gas grid pressure to achieve a sustainable balance, maximum

availability, and security of supply. To address these objectives, the following research questions have been answered in this report.

- What is the standard procedure to guarantee security of supply of the gas feeder?
- How to dynamically control the pressure at the gas feeder to increase the feed-in flow limit and increase the uptime of the gas feeder?
- What is the strategy to control (multiple) gas feeder prioritization for balancing the gas grid?
- How will the control algorithm be affected when there is more flexibility in the system due to storage, flexible demand, and intermittent supply?

In general, from a technical perspective, there are several options that can be used for controlling the grid by utilizing the grid flexibility throughout the value chain, e.g.:

- **Supply:** ability to deploy flexible supply in order to level off the peak with flexible hydrogen production, e.g., electrolyzers using power grid when there is no solar or wind and curtail production when there is a surplus of renewables.
- **Demand:** demand side management where it can shift the use of hydrogen from a peak situation by utilizing other commodities, e.g., electricity for heating or an internal buffer.
- **Storage:** utilizing the use of local storage or pipeline storage (linepack).
- **Booster:** bring the surplus gas in the low-pressure network to a higher-pressure network.
- **Prioritization:** dynamic pressure management to prioritize which feeder can supply to the grid.

Not all of options above were evaluated in this report. We analysed two different networks: a) multiple cities hydrogen grid and b) standalone industrial hydrogen grid. Several observations and conclusions can be derived from the simulations and analysis regarding main lessons learned and guidelines for asset management with multiple local feed-in and dynamic supply and demand.

1. A transient analysis tool is needed to understand the system dynamics

Both case studies Uden-Mill (domestic area) and H2avennet (industrial area) show that the linepack capacity of the network is too small compared to the feeder flow variations. Thus, when there is an imbalance in supply/demand, there is a fast reaction (within minutes) needed in order to maintain the pressure in operating conditions. While a static solver is enough for network capacity planning, the transient solver can help DSOs to design the control strategy of their grid management (flow balancing, pressure dynamics, etc.). Especially in the case of emergency or a sudden failure. Next to the safety components already available in the grid to prevent damage to the grid and the customers.

2. Static pressure management is not straight forward when there is local feeder, but it can be done

When the network is only having WOS, static pressure management may be sufficient for managing the grid (two different setpoint pressures: during winter and summer). However, it is not straight forward in case there is an additional local feeder. Since the demand and supply has high uncertainties (weather dependent), it is unclear when one should change the setpoint pressure and how many times in a year due to big difference in minimum flow and maximum flow demand in a year. Because, it will affect the local feeder if the pressure is too high and it will affect the Overstlagstation if the pressure is too low. For example from the year 2022 data, there is low demand in March, then high demand in April and low demand again in May. It means that you need to switch 3 times.

3. Dynamic pressure management is a more robust solution compared to static pressure but requires more technologies

Since there is a lot of uncertainty in weather (for production and demand), utilizing dynamic pressure management can be a robust solution because the grid is dynamically controlled to react in the current situation. However, this method requires more flow and pressure sensors implementation to get real-time data of network information, real-time algorithm/calculations to determine the flow and pressure setpoint at regulators and remote actuators for controlling valve. The dynamic pressure management is not the ultimate solution if the network complexity is high and having to many local feeders. Thus, combination with other methods is recommended. The dynamic pressure management can't be done only by DSO, it needs TSO and DSO collaboration.

4. Setpoint pressure of the WOS can be utilized to increase capacity and uptime of the hydrogen feeder

To increase the capacity and uptime of the hydrogen feeder during the low demand season, one can set the setpoint pressure of the WOS close to minimum pipeline pressure compared to the setting during high demand season where the setpoint pressure is close to maximum pipeline pressure. Thus, there is not enough room for hydrogen feeder's delta pressure. The higher delta pressure, the more capacity can be facilitated.

5. Setpoint pressure control can be deployed for feeder prioritization

Priority of the WOS and feeder can be set by putting the correct setpoint pressure for their pressure regulator. With help of a simulation tool, one can estimate what is the pressure required for WOS and feeder in order to produce with a certain flow. Since the supplier will shut down when the downstream pressure is higher than the setpoint pressure (lockup pressure), one can prioritize by giving the lowest setpoint pressure to the lowest priority feeder and the highest setpoint pressure to the highest priority feeder. In the current regulation, first come first served basis is used to determine the priority of the feeder. There is a limit of maximum number of feeders, depends on complexity of the network, that can be regulated by using setpoint pressure. However, finding this limit is out of scope of this study.

6. A booster can be used to increase local feeder uptime, but not in every location

Booster implementation can increase the uptime of the local feeder to help continuously flowing because the flow surplus is injected back to the higher pressure network (TSO). However, it shows that not every location is optimal for booster location. It is recommended to implement a booster near to the local feeder area to avoid a high pressure drop due to distance. E.g. in the Uden-Mill network, only two locations are recommended to install a booster station, either the Mill area or Uden area. The rest of the cities are too far from the feeder and has too small pipeline diameter, thus generating too high pressure drop in the network. The booster station is usually installed near WOS or higher pressure pipeline (RTL).

7. Surface storage is not a practical solution due to seasonal imbalance

Another option to increase the uptime of the feeder is by utilizing surface storage. However as we can see from the demand profile of e.g. Uden-Mill, the feeder flow contract is always higher than the total demand for a couple of months (July-September). It requires to store hydrogen around 6 Mm³ at 1 bar, equivalent to 22 km³ tanks storage if it is compressed at 350 bar (and additional compressor equipment needed). In case of daily to weekly storage more practical solutions will be available.

4.3. General Conclusion

The research activities done in this HyDelta3 work package and a case study in two different networks give several insights in how to control the future hydrogen grid in case there will be more distributed

local hydrogen feeders. The digitalization, e.g. monitoring of the network through sensors, modelling network's behaviour using gas network simulation tool and advising control strategies through algorithm, can help to design a more robust grid or improve operational excellence. The profile-based simulation tool can help the grid operator to make decision about which solution should be implemented to increase the capacity and controlling the feeders. Based on measurement data from past years and weather profiles, we can predict the consumption profiles. Then we can determine the period and with capacity in a year where the feeder supply is higher than the total demand. Thus, DSOs can determine which solution should be implemented: e.g. a booster station, curtailment of the feeder, pressure management or surface/sub-surface storage. The most effective solution to have the local hydrogen feeder always be able to feed to the grid is by implementing a booster station. However, if this is not a feasible solution, then the next solution to increase capacity of the local hydrogen feeder by combination of storage, curtailment or pressure management.

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